

Workshop 07.05.2024

Whaley, Paul

So just a quick refresher of where we're at in our process. So as you know, I should hope you know we're developing invites in which is a tool for assessing the internal validity of an in vitro study by internal validity. We mean the potential for systematic error in results or findings and will be the intent is for this tool to be used in systematic reviews of in vitro studies.

Whaley, Paul

Which I've done for kind of toxicology purposes. What we've done so far is collect potential bias criteria from existing study assessment assessment tools. So that was our literature review component and from expert opinion, which was our focus group component and what we're doing now was to prioritising items for inclusion in the draught invites in tool.

Whaley, Paul

Using a modified Delphi approach.

Whaley, Paul

As you will definitely be aware, there are a lot of items that went through the Dell fee.

Whaley, Paul

Not all of those items, of course, achieved consensus for being either appropriate or not for evaluating internal, virtual and in vitro study. So that was 166, in fact, where we didn't have.

Whaley, Paul

A clear consensus of the site should be in or out. So what we're going to do in these post Delphi discussions is discuss with you these items.

Whaley, Paul

To inform the research group to change decisions on how we to handle them. So we're not going to make any decisions today on how an item is going to be handled. We just want to get a better understanding of the issues that.

Whaley, Paul

You were struggling with, which would explain the lack of consensus that we can then use when we analyse this remaining set of 166 and make in our decisions of our own right.

Whaley, Paul

It's not perfect, but it's the best we can do. We think with the resources that we've got.

Whaley, Paul

So what we'll do is we'll discuss and clarify with you what the items might mean in relation to in vitro studies and your opinion is their importance for introducing systematic error into a study. We're not at this stage discussing whether or not we should be in the final tool as such, because the tool will look very different to the items. The items are just concepts. So it's just whether the concepts expressed might be important for introducing bias in an in vitro study, OK. Does that sound like it makes sense to you all?

Whaley, Paul

Some nods.

Whaley, Paul

So we've got 12 domains that we're going to be working through. Obviously, we won't go through all of those today. We've prepared all the way up to detection bias. That will be 6 domains that will probably be more than enough if it's we do get all the way through, then we'll just stop the session early. But I'd be very surprised if you manage that.

Whaley, Paul

So yes, we've got analysis bias, attrition bias, choice of question bias completed and trust bias combined grow bias and the rest that you will have seen in the Delphi process. So the way the discussion is going to work is I'm going to show you the domain, the definition of the domain and the number of items were under that domain. We weren't able to achieve consensus through Delphi. Then what we'll do is we'll have a structured discussion of the items that are grouped according to common issues in relation to comments from the Delphi or the focus of the items.

Whaley, Paul

Right. So again, these are just, this is not intended to be a true description of how the items relate to each other. It really is just kind of like a crutch for helping us have a discussion.

Whaley, Paul

We're gonna prioritise identifying where items have poor consensus because they were unclear. Then get a sense of what direction we should go in once that view of the meaning of the item is clearer, right? So we'll be asking you for your ideas on that, since we've got through discussion groups, each group will be discussing different domains. The domains are there to structure the discussion, so we're not at this point discussing whether the domains there are an appropriate or optimal or complete classification scheme for biases.

Whaley, Paul

It's just a crutch just to help us have a structured discussion as to say the final tool will probably look quite different to why the items are being presented at this time.

Whaley, Paul

Yes.

Whaley, Paul

In terms of administrative information, as you know, the session is being recorded and machine transcribed.

Whaley, Paul

Data will be anonymized and we would ask you not to attribute comments to specific individuals after this call. OK, so it's Chatham House rules job. I'm your facilitator.

Whaley, Paul

And Goon is helping with steering the facilitation.

Whaley, Paul

Crew is your note, a note taker today and also the project supervisor and lead. So if you have any questions or concerns about the process, if you could raise a nail, that would be very helpful. If you have questions or concerns that you don't want to raise now, want to raise later, please e-mail group about those. Is that all clear? Good everybody reasonably happy.

Whaley, Paul

Very good. So we can get cracking then. So quick recording check.

Whaley, Paul

You have my gravelly tones transcribed for all time. Fantastic.

Whaley, Paul

So analysis bias is the first domain that we're going to look at. There were nineteen items under analysis bias where we weren't able to achieve consensus and we define analysis bias as a bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.

Whaley, Paul

So you've got data, you analyse it, bias in analysis bias is any bias is introduced by those processes analysing data.

Whaley, Paul

So the themes that came through, uh, the Delphi that seem to be difficult to deal with or challenging to deal with, I should say, relate to your software choices.

Whaley, Paul

And then some issues relating to normalisation, pre processing and noise and data reduction in the data.

Whaley, Paul

What are called correction factors in in the items, which is about adjusting data for some reason or another.

Whaley, Paul

Then we were there were an items about the absence of predictors of missing data and making sure that those are appropriately handled.

Whaley, Paul

Blinding and prior knowledge of data analysis potentially introducing bias and then some aspects of like data model. So that might be number of features.

Whaley, Paul

That some maybe machine learning based process or regression or something. So the number of features that is trained on are not necessarily being appropriate and then like dichotomization of say continuous data which may also introduce bias.

Whaley, Paul

So did you have any thoughts or questions at this stage? Next slide, I'm gonna show you some specific examples, but at just this point, is this ring any bells? Do you have any thoughts or comments as it related to the delphi process and these sorts of ideas as it relates to potential for bias and in vitro studies?

Whaley, Paul

You got a participant shaking her head. participant. It's grinning like a lunatic and shaking his head. I'm not sure what that means, but is this like, you're just waiting for the next slide, or do you have thoughts?

Yeah. Oh, makes makes makes sense. But I mean, no, no comment so far.

0:8:45.850 --> 0:8:47.650

Whaley, Paul

No comments so far.

No, not really. It it it rings the several bells I would say.

Whaley, Paul
Very good.

Except machine learning, which I'm I'm not so proficient in.

Whaley, Paul
Oh well, me neither. So uh huh?

Whaley, Paul
Good. So some of the specific items obviously we had like 19, I just haven't pulled them all out. These were sort of fairly representative of some of the things we can go and look in detail at the spreadsheet that was shared with you, if you want to do that as well. So just just shout if you would like to do that in terms of specific items we had one about controlling for other factors measured after the start of the exposure window. There was an item on absence from the analysis model of predictors of.

Whaley, Paul
Missingness of exposure data.

Whaley, Paul
That was an item on noise attenuation. A nice one dichotomization of continuous data and an item model analysis for estimating effect of adhering to the exposure. So these presented different issues as far as we could tell from the comments.

Whaley, Paul
They want to start from the top, but maybe if we think about this item was controlling for other factors.

Whaley, Paul
Just to go find it for myself.

Whaley, Paul
OK.

Whaley, Paul
So in terms of why that might have been unclear.

Whaley, Paul
Do you have any thoughts or comments? It might just be that it's completely unclear and we don't need to use it. participant.

Is I'm thinking it could it be, for instance, if you're studying hormones and then there could be?

Hormones in feed of of animals, for instance.

Is it that type of thing, except that this is in vitro, so you have to relate it to something else like for, for instance.

I'm working with.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

With the optical radiation in combination with chemicals.

That means there are several things I have to control, and if I work with cells and I use a medium that can very some components can absorb visible light. For instance, I have a problem, so that means that when I am irradiating the the cell dishes, I need to use a medium that cannot absorb.

The visible light.

Whaley, Paul

OK. Yep.

Whaley, Paul

I do, yes, yes.

It's do you do you understand what I mean? So. So there is. Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

So this so one of the. So this item did come from I think I think it came from Robin's E which is a instrument for assessing risk of bias in observational studies. And the reason that there are two reasons for including this first reason was that we were told to by our expert group. And the second reason is that it's potentially relates to.

Whaley, Paul

In vitro studies that have primary cell cultures, so you get your students to come into the lab, you you drain them of blood, I believe is the technical description technical term for this. And then obviously you kind of culture that what I don't know you take skin samples or like cheek samples or whatever and you create a culture from that. So then it might be important to understand some aspects of how the use of people in your study from whom you're taking samples could introduce confounding.

Whaley, Paul

In this particular case, I think the that Robbins was concerned with when you're following people through a study that somehow.

Whaley, Paul

The what they're exposed to and how they behave and additional prognostic factors and whatnot can somehow introduce confounding that you need to.

Whaley, Paul

Measure and make sense of. So it sounds like in the in the vitro context there might be something analogous in how.

Whaley, Paul

Some aspect of the experimental environment can interfere with another aspect, right? As he was saying.

Whaley, Paul

But we're not really sure yet. I think it's to as to how to interpret this. Did anybody else have any thoughts? So Participant, or am I?

No, but the example you gave obviously there it will be important, but I think it's.

That's BOOP, would you, when you would work with.

With primary cultures or with patients for example, but I I think for majority of in vitro studies it's not going to be applicable because most of the times I mean what I'm thinking it's like using cell lines or things like that where most likely they wouldn't be a lot of factors afterwards but.

I mean would be important to know if there are.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So it might be something that we do is we might view the.

Whaley, Paul

Tool that we create as being modular, right? So there'll be some questions that are always applicable and there'll be some questions that are only applicable to specific.

Whaley, Paul

Research contacts, so it might be that there's like a primary cell cultures module for the tool, so we don't want to dismiss something as at this point just because it's only occasionally relevant. If it's always relevant in those occasions, we may still want to account for it some way as we engineer the tool.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I think, uh, I think we're getting to the bottom of this. Uh, I do. You have any any thoughts on this?

No, I I agree with what I said before. For me, it was also a little bit, yeah, just to phrasing made it difficult to to grasp what it was exactly referring to.

Whaley, Paul

That is fair enough. Yeah, it was kind of expected because obviously we're trying to strip out as much unnecessary language as possible. So we could tell when we had two items that are about the same concept, but the trade off was that of course, is it made them a little bit difficult to understand out of context. So appreciate your patience as we kind of go through this. So then if we move on to abstinence from analysis model of predictors of missingness of exposure data.

Whaley, Paul

This, I'm afraid I don't have a clue about, so I'm hoping that maybe something would be to shed some light so this has something to do with.

Whaley, Paul

Something about?

Whaley, Paul

Making sure that.

Whaley, Paul

Predictors, which I think work a bit like confounders in the model, are fully accommodated, but I don't know how this works in in vitro studies.

Whaley, Paul

And how much, I guess how much modelling is involved in an in vitro study, so when?

Whaley, Paul

'Cause I might maybe run out 'cause you're working with ontags right then. Umm. To what? What extent does the use of uh making predictions?

Whaley, Paul

Inform or how much does it in vitro study? Maybe rest on those predictions? Or if you've got 9 predictors in your system that you have to adjust for these? Or is this just not a relevant consideration?

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm mm hmm.

So I mean, OK, let's let's so first of all, let's try maybe from the general perspective. So the the way I understand it is it's somehow contains the idea that if you if if basically exposure data is not missing randomly but there's some correlation of the missingness that this might somehow bias I guess in the end.

Your you know some, some kind of analysis model. But I mean for me, I think the big problem is here that it was something that I guess.

It seems intuitive that this is important, but I guess the the critical question is, in which context can we imagine? Or do you? Do we imagine actually the situation to occur? What kind of analysis model does it refer to?

I guess this is where for me the the phrasing creates some difficulty because I'm not, I'm not quite sure it's. It's like something that seems important as a general concept, but I'm not quite sure. Practically speaking what you know example I'm supposed to think of when I read this this item.

Whaley, Paul
So when you say, it's important, generally speaking. So I mean I I forgot to preface as well, I'm going to ask some questions that sound amazingly stupid. It's just a facilitation process. So I'm just being professionally stupid. So when you say like the general principle, do you want to just explain what you think the general principle is here and then maybe we might be able to move from that to specific examples?

Whaley, Paul
Right I can.

Yeah. Well, I mean, I'm not quite sure how to how to say it differently than the way I said it already.

Whaley, Paul
Yep.

Is it? Yeah, we're trying to say it in a different way. I'm trying to to.

Remember and visualise some experiments, but could it be, for instance, if you you're making a dose response curve?

So.

You have some exposure that you, let's say you have to interpolate and you haven't been able to get all your data points.

And but you have from previous experience. For instance you think this is a linear correlation, but it turns out with this specific.

Experiment. It's you. Have you, you. You get an S shape instead, for instance and.

And you haven't taken that into account before you started. Could it be something like that?

I I I think that.

The question is horribly phrased.

That mean it has to be something some something like this. But I mean it also has to be a situation where you have.

A bias for. So basically you have to have a situation with the exposure. Data is not missing randomly right? So it has to be a situation where there's some systematic error that makes you lack the exposure data in certain situations.

Yeah.

But I mean, couldn't that just be that you for example like you're missing? Like I'm thinking about the screening screening approaches where they just take exposures where different?

Yes, they have like, you know one one third or so in between and then you might miss some really important parts where if I'm just thinking like you know you you actually should have taken like much smaller steps in in between 2:00 because that's where the point of departure is.

Isn't. Couldn't that be then the missing of the exposure data? And because I mean, if you do screening approaches, you normally don't go back and redo?

The experiment 'cause it's just.

I mean I I.

I think.

It's not meant for that. It's just as a screening purpose. And then you you could go back afterwards and do more detailed studies. But I'm wondering if that could be, but it's I agree completely that this this sentence has really absence from the analysis model. Predictors are missingness of? Yeah.

Yeah, exactly. I mean it kind of makes sense to me, but then it's not really even. It's even that case. It wouldn't be a systematic bias, right? It would just be sort of you have you are sampling too costly basically, but you don't, I don't, I don't see how in this context it will lead to a systematic bias. You know what I mean?

You do the prediction if you make the the curve.

If you're missing a lot, I mean it would could be biased that you would get a different curve than if you would have had.

More data points just.

I agree.

Exactly. But this would be a random bias again, right? I mean, sometimes maybe.

At my, or at least I can't imagine a situation then.

I I can't think of the reason why it would not be just a random.

Error you know.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I think so. I think what this item was trying to get at and I I agree that it's badly phrased and just very difficult to wrap your head around is that it's something about there being an association between.

Whaley, Paul

There's some structure to the missing data.

Whaley, Paul

That needs to be allowed for when modelling it in some way.

Whaley, Paul

So if you missed that structure, then you're going to in some way that censorship is going to affect your whatever your results of your analysis is. But I can't. I can't think of what it is. It's not my job, but it may just be that this is just too too strange and we don't really need to worry about it. Is my hunch at this point.

Whaley, Paul

We figure it out better later, maybe in version two of everything.

Whaley, Paul

So maybe we can move on. Sorry. Yep.

Maybe just just one last comment, 11 idea that's coming to my mind right now, maybe this could be also in in principle conceptually be related to sort of in vitro kinetics to a situation where you try to account for you know sort of in vitro.

Distribution of chemicals and that maybe for some chemicals, you know, maybe when you try to measure the concentration really in your in vitro system that for some chemicals you're not able to do that because the chemicals for some reason.

Distributing to, I don't know the plastics or operating or whatever and that there is a structural or systemic bias then in this measurement in your attempt sort of to correct for this because it's certain classes of chemicals.

Where you structurally then can't? Can't make this measurement. I mean again, OK, this is it's very it's very, I don't know. It's very difficult for me to to, to, to think of what you know obviously situations maybe I'm already interpreting too much into this item to be honest.

Whaley, Paul

Well, I mean, I think we can say about everything we want into it, right? They're trying to figure out what it means for us. So that that sounds like that could make sense. So we've captured that so.

Whaley, Paul

Let's move on to noise attenuation. So the comments on this were like, why does noise matter to in vitro studies? I think that may have been a misunderstanding that it wasn't like.

Whaley, Paul

Noise for your ears. It was noise in relation to data.

Whaley, Paul

participant.

Yes, because I am when measuring light.

Whaley, Paul

Hmm.

There's a lot about the light today and then we of course have a darker and in the in the, in the detector or in the instruments. So we always have to remove that or or disregard that. So everything

that is measured above that level is real light. But what's below, which just look like some blurry thing, it's not measured and it's important to know where that level is.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

So that should be reported.

Whaley, Paul

So does that relate to then? So 'cause we had these like, I'm just gonna go back on one of themselves. We had these.

Whaley, Paul

Four things that this just the single one is supposed to be representing. It's got normalisation, pre processing and noise and data reduction techniques.

Hmm.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

Absolutely, I found it quite surprising that people sort of felt that this was maybe not important for bias. So do you have any insight as to maybe why people might have felt this was unimportant? Perhaps.

Whaley, Paul

And you'd be 3.

Did you ask me?

Whaley, Paul

Anybody. But if you want anyone can answer so yeah.

Yeah. No. Yeah, I I I can just continue because I think this is also the same.

Chromatography, for instance. Another different kinds of analysis technique. So maybe it's because people haven't been exposed to it or haven't used it.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Whaley, Paul

I'm just. I 'cause I'm. I'm again. I'm not familiar with a lot of lab scientists, so when it when you're doing an in vitro study, how much like, you know, in terms of avalanche of data where you've got stuff in there that you're trying to eliminate because it's it's not meaningful, but you know, instrumentation is twitching, right, versus trying to kind of isolate the true signal say like.

Whaley, Paul

Well, I guess what can go wrong there? How can it introduce bias? What would you want to see somebody reporting to make sure that you are confident that there was an error introduced by those data reduction techniques?

Whaley, Paul

I think participant or participant, do you have any thoughts on that?

Well, I mean.

To me, you don't really. I don't know when you would remove the the noise. You would take it in consideration when you are doing your analysis, right? So I don't see, I think no one.

But unless what you, I mean, if it's below the threshold, I don't know if you call it noise then I would say it's just you need to have a clear understanding when a real effect is happening. I mean normally what we're doing looking at the baseline of.

And variability within the control situation or sometimes even with the lower concentrations and that's how you set your.

Your your your model for deciding for your prediction model, for, for for what is with what is a hit, so I don't. Maybe that's why people didn't understand what it meant.

I can.

Since your question was it, I mean.

I I also think this, I think in principle it's obviously important, but I think there's a, yeah, a large variety of situations that people might have been thinking of. I think in some situations, you know it's it's, yeah, something you have to deal with manually. But in other situations, I think it's, you know, even when you're analysing data, you really have, you know, very, very established packages for the data analysis that have very established mathematical and statistical methods.

That are quite.

And yeah, quite reliable and in principle, trusted very much by people. And I think for this reason people might have thought, OK, no, this this, you know, from this it's almost just a technical thing that is not so worrying. And for that reason that people might have felt OK actually this is just a technical thing.

Maybe it's not support?

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

OK, participant.

Yes, I just a follow up to participant's comments there. I I think that you you this is a could be a very important point because when I discussed this in because I'm also in.

Working with standardisation and I I think it's fair to say that the the age.

The mean age of the participants is rather high and.

So.

When I say that, well, my instrument is capturing this automatically then other could be other attendants, attendances, attendees who are or participants who will say that you know it's not. It's not like that because they have been doing it in a different way for the last 50 years. So it has to do with the, you know, the new technology.

And think somewhere more automatic now than it used to be, so that could be a part of it. So I think when they have the very good point.

Whaley, Paul

It's kind of a calibration issue that it starts edging into you.

Whaley, Paul

Calibration machine, yeah.

Everything is. It's becoming easier. Yeah. Yeah. But I still think that the question and noise attenuation, it should be more specifically phrased.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, of course. Yeah. Well, I mean, there's a whole cluster of concepts surrounding this that will will aggregate into something like meaningful and comprehensive.

Whaley, Paul

Is there anything that we should be aware of while thinking about when it comes to data cleansing that springs to mind?

Whaley, Paul

Like if you got again. I don't really know how this works but.

Whaley, Paul

If you've got messy data that needs tidying up before you do anything serious with it.

Whaley, Paul

Is that a similar issue to noise attenuation or is that kind of because going to be treated a bit differently?

Whaley, Paul

M.

Yeah. I I I think it's that's very, very overlapping and I guess the question is just really what situation do you think of and I mean you know again just to give an example for noise attenuation, right, if you think about about you know image analysis of some, if you have some essay and then do have microscopy and then you do image segmentation and automatic sort of image analysis, then many of these packages and and what happens technically.

In the in the software where you have to deal with the noise.

Coming in, you know, happening in the image, a lot of it really is just technical and if it's that situation, probably really is not so relevant. But then if you think what other essays the noise can really make the difference potentially.

Between, you know, having a hit, having not a hit, and and that's just a huge spectrum.

That this item was sort of addressing.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good. I think we can, I think we can handle this. So then dichotomisation of continuous data so.

Whaley, Paul

This one surprised me that we didn't get consensus. I have to say it seems to me to be fairly

important, but I don't know if you have any thoughts as to why maybe there wasn't consensus on this.

Whaley, Paul

Or do you just think it's obviously important? Tell me one way or the other.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah, maybe I can go fast. I think it's important. And I struggle to think of why people might think it's not important.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

And yes, if I understand the question right, it means that you have you have continuous data and you're trying to.

Stick optimised them right.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm. Yep.

And so I don't know if I have never done that so.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I wouldn't know how how to do that, but I'm sure I would. It would be very important to to report how how this is taken care of.

Otherwise, it seems to be very random.

Maybe I can get some.

Education here.

Whaley, Paul

And look at me. participant. Do you have any thoughts?

No, I'm. I'm with participant there. I also I never did that I but obviously if you do that you need to have clear criterias why and how and.

Like with everything, right? You need to justify and a preferable.

Before.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Actually, maybe I can think of one thing, maybe maybe people thought that this item is not about the way that you do with dichotomization, but if it's if it's a problem to do it in general or not. And people were reading it and saying no, I think it's not a problem that you do that.

And for that reason said, maybe it's unimportant.

Whaley, Paul
M.

You know what I mean, semantically.

Whaley, Paul
Yeah, maybe. Yep.

Whaley, Paul
That would be an explanation. So we think it's important we think we have an explanation as to why there was.

Whaley, Paul
Lack of consensus, so I think that that satisfies me. So let's move on to the next domain. So attrition bias, 12 items, so not so much challenge here maybe so this is a bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.

Whaley, Paul
So I'll just give you 2 seconds to think about that.

Whaley, Paul
Have any questions please ask.

May I ask you?

So. So this is often the case where you have, for instance, if you had an animal experiment then then you say you have 20 animals and then you record or you yeah report results for only let's say half of them without any explanation.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

Would that be? Yeah. OK. Yeah. OK. Spell with.

Whaley, Paul
That would be an example of attrition. Yes. So yeah. So you're losing subjects from your study.

Yeah. So yeah, so in an in vitro study that would be you, you start with the 12 dishes and you end up with 10 and you're not saying that you lost the other two on the floor. OK.

Whaley, Paul
So I'm like, well, I don't happen to him right, but Yep.

Whaley, Paul
That is correct, yes. So then the bias would be any any systematic error that is introduced by trician. So random attrition is generally OK.

Whaley, Paul
Non random attrition is problematic.

Whaley, Paul
Yeah. So there are a couple of issues that came through on this. So we had.

Whaley, Paul
Things that relates to, say, incomplete data on participants and I think a lot of that hinged on this concept of participants and what that means right because.

Whaley, Paul

Even some of the in vitro specific tools that we included in our literature review, still talked about participants because researchers do all kinds of weird stuff, right. So obviously at all like Robbins, E are being for human observational research talks about participants. So I think that some in the issue here may have been that people just didn't really know how to interpret participant in the context of vitro because obviously in a cell culture isn't participating as such.

Whaley, Paul

It's more the subject or object of study or something, right?

Whaley, Paul

Unless it's a primary cell culture, of course, then you've got study subject attrition rates and reasons. So that was the attrition thing. And then you just nicely summarised.

Whaley, Paul

And then there's this issue of handling of dependencies between missing data and what would be measured.

Whaley, Paul

Or would have been measured if that data weren't missing, right? So this might be I think probably I have a hunch that what this means is something about like, you know, if the results of the test is positive.

Whaley, Paul

There's some correlation between data being missing and being positive, right? So then you get an over ponderance the negative results and you're bias down.

Whaley, Paul

So do you have any thoughts or comments on any of these?

Whaley, Paul

So I just I vocalise some of this sometimes. So for the gets on the transcript because we can't transcript to your gestures obviously.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Yeah, I mean, makes sense. I remember. Listen, I remember some confusion about this, this question items.

Whaley, Paul

Yes, OK. So if you guys, the specific some of the specific items so.

Whaley, Paul

Incomplete data on outcome status of participants. So if we substituted.

Whaley, Paul

I don't know study subjects or cell cultures or wells or something for participants. Would that make it clearer what this meant?

Yes, samples maybe.

Whaley, Paul

Examples. That's good one you can tell. I'm a lab researcher, can't you?

That does agree.

Whaley, Paul

Good. And then when it Yep. Agreed. And then when it comes to description of dropouts, so again would do you think drop out would be the challenging term here and that it would be description maybe of excluded or missing samples or something?

Whaley, Paul

Good. So we have two, three nods.

Yeah, excluding.

Whaley, Paul

You're good. OK. And then differences between exposure groups and reason for missing outcome data.

Whaley, Paul

Do you have any thoughts on that?

Whaley, Paul

You know, challenges and interpretation or.

Whaley, Paul

Thoughts as to why? Maybe there wasn't consensus or what you think could be changed to achieve consensus.

To be honest, I'm not quite sure, I mean yet. I think again if you.

Sort of think of exposure groups as people then that's probably confusing, but and then if you exchange that, it's probably better, but it's also longer than the ones before and seems to be kind of a similar as the ones before. And I think this is probably something people struggle with when they wear multiple items that seem very similar.

To each other, and then they were not sure you know which of them potentially try to emphasise what kind of, you know, special case or specific sort of.

I don't know. Yeah. How do you say it's in English?

Whaley, Paul

Yep.

Yeah.

There we go.

Whaley, Paul

That's fair enough.

Yeah, I'm surprised though that because this one I feel is is pretty clear. Even if you would have in vitro system. So for me it would be clear, yes, this is extremely important. I mean if you have.

Two in one group and five in the other, obviously.

That will be biased.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul
Very good.

Whaley, Paul
OK. And then this one is just probably much more challenging censorship of follow up on change to assigned exposure. So again, I've have a feeling this came from the Robins tool. So it's much more focused on human participants and therefore may not be relevant to our context.

Whaley, Paul
Unless you have an in vitro study design.

Whaley, Paul
Where for whatever reason, there is a change in exposure assignment halfway through the study.

Whaley, Paul
Because that would happen in people is that you'd be giving them one drug and maybe they don't react it very well. So you change their treatment because you don't want them to be harmed by their participation in the study. So you need to allow for that somehow in your.

Whaley, Paul
Making sense of the, you know, average outcomes for participants.

Whaley, Paul
That can introduce bias if you don't handle it very well, but I'm just thinking, is there any analogous circumstances in vitro study unless it was with primary cell cultures or something? So you're taking self cultures from people who were involved in a study of humans and you were using in vitro methods for measuring outcomes and things. Can you think of any circumstance where this change in a signed exposure might be relevant, or do you think this just doesn't relate to in vitro?

And maybe if you wanna do like a follow up hit or something like you would do one exposure first and then you would change to a second exposure afterwards. But I don't know if people are.

Whaley, Paul
Would that be done selectively, or would you just do a follow up hit on the whole label set of wells or something?

Yeah, I mean I I don't, I don't think it's it's.

I I I don't think this is a common thing for me to in that sense, because I mean it doesn't matter and that you would do it just randomly if you would have a follow up exposures. I didn't, I don't think it would be.

I agree.

Whaley, Paul
OK, so maybe this is one that we can sort of exclude as being not relevant then. So it's difficult to understand and probably doesn't relate to anything that might make sense. Yeah, OK.

I agree on that.

Whaley, Paul
Yes. Well, we'll get rid of one of these. That's it. That's gonna make our life a slightly easier.

Whaley, Paul

1/4 of a percent. So then the final one here is this idea of data loss due to labelling errors.

Whaley, Paul

Is there any way in which that would introduce systematic error? Or do you have any experience of labelling errors resulting in potential for bias like seen, it heard of it done it yourself.

Whaley, Paul

Hmm.

I mean if if you don't know what your sample is, then you have to start experiment over again.

You can't use it, I mean.

Whaley, Paul

And what might happen is that the role label is on a sample, right?

Yeah, but and I I I have. I'm yeah, I attended.

Or I participated in in an animal experiment. When that happened and and you realise that someone had labelled.

Yeah, the groups incorrectly, but that went we just had to do it all over again.

So I I cannot if you if you don't know what you have. I mean, you can't use it so.

How how would you? You can't report that. I mean, how will you detect that in a in a in a study? How are you going to evaluate risk of bias?

Yeah.

They wouldn't say. I mean, that's more heating.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, they wouldn't just no one would know, right? Yep.

Yeah.

Oh, I agree.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I would also think this is probably then where the where the differences in in people's ratings come from, that people probably think yes, OK, it could introduce a systematic error in a specific study, but practically speaking, is it relevant? Not really, because how would you ever evaluate this externally after it has been done? I mean therefore from a practical perspective, it's not relevant. Although of course theoretically, if you could get that information, sure, it would be nice, but.

Whaley, Paul

The kind of undetectable, catastrophic error that completely blows the results of the study and uh Yep.

Whaley, Paul

Very good. OK.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, it's a tricky one. It's when you're in the realm of maybe a benign, unintentional error that has the equivalent of fraudulent documentation or something, because it's undetectable. It's from human error, not as on purpose, but you like you just, yeah, stuff the study in a quite unique way. OK, we'll think about that.

I mean it it it, it's just in a in a single study it would give you of course a systematic error. But overall if you think about all the studies that are being performed, it should hopefully be something random and and therefore overall it should be not a systematic error if you think about.

Whaley, Paul

I'm not sure I share your confidence, but yes, hopefully eventually someone would have done enough replications that the very large effect size deserved in this one off instance maybe gets identified as an outlier, right?

Whaley, Paul

Hopefully.

Whaley, Paul

Good. OK, so next, uh, domain is choice of question bias, so this is hopefully slightly easier. 'cause, we've only got 4 items in it. There were, there was a lack of consensus. So this is a bias and research design in which the research question that the study is designed to answer is inappropriate for the context.

Whaley, Paul

OK, so ask asking tricky questions. Basically, so does that make sense to you? First question, good, but three nods. So we had, I think, 3 themes across these four items.

Whaley, Paul

So there was a a thing that relates to completeness of test of hypothesis. So that's where.

Whaley, Paul

You're only partially testing the hypothesis, but maybe presenting it as a complete test of hypothesis.

Whaley, Paul

Frame of question.

Whaley, Paul

And then framing of context.

Whaley, Paul

So do you have any thoughts or recollections relating to these that you or any comments that you'd like to make at this point?

Yes, I I wonder does this have anything to do with the relevance?

Like framing the context then I'm thinking more a weight of evidence.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm mm hmm.

That would be evaluated after a risk of bias. Or do I misunderstand?

Whaley, Paul

No, no, I don't think so. I think it could do potentially.

Whaley, Paul

There are some areas where it's just it's difficult to know where best to handle it, right. So if you've got, if you've got a study like if we're thinking about, you know, the potential for false positives or false negatives in the results and findings of the study. If the question is framed in such a way that the.

Whaley, Paul

The findings of the study end up being, you know, end up being interpreted as positive or negative. When that's not true. And that relates to the question that that could be viewed as being internal to the study design rather than a matter of inference from the study to different contexts outside that study, right.

Whaley, Paul

I don't. I don't have any specific examples of when this is in play.

Whaley, Paul

It's just something that does come up sometimes and it's definitely we know that it doesn't come very often and study assessment tools and things.

Whaley, Paul

But it did. You know, we just wanted to get a sense of how important people felt this was.

Whaley, Paul

Maybe for risk of bias instrument is not important.

Whaley, Paul

Let's go on. Just have a quick look at some of these, uh, specific items that we didn't get consensus. So if we look at incomplete tests of the hypothesis.

Whaley, Paul

Would that be something that maybe you've seen?

Whaley, Paul

Umm.

Whaley, Paul

Does it?

Whaley, Paul

Does it relate to trying to understand risk of bias in a systematic review?

Whaley, Paul

I just trying to think.

I'm not sure because normally like.

Incomplete test of the of the hypothesis. Most most of the times you.

You always have to do follow up things. I mean, it's very. I mean, if you have, unless you have a very clear specific question like.

I think you use like a weight of evidence approach. Anyway, it's never like so I'm not sure if it's really a risk of bias in that sense. I would more say.

That's why we always try to be vague when we are interpreting our results, right? So it 'cause we always know that we will find more information going forward. So I don't know if I think it's a.

Risk of bias in this sense.

I'm thinking a little bit about imprecision as well.

So that could be evaluated also as part of weight of evidence because.

Now I'm thinking OK.

Back-to-back to optics again.

If I irradiate samples with some type of irradiation and and I was mistaken, I I needed another spectrum.

And then my results would be.

It well, if I didn't know what that I had the wrong spectrum then I would get results that were different from from what I had been thinking or what I mean what I was trying to achieve.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm mm.

So I was testing the hypothesis that I said I was.

But but that would be imprecision.

And then for in vitro, I think I've, I've put a read on the experiment rather than to to.

To walk the part of shame.

Whaley, Paul

So maybe one way of thinking about this is if, like keeping it simple for people like me, imagine that there's a hypothesis that.

Whaley, Paul

Given chemical challenge is not a pathotoxic right and then there are six measures of liver toxicity and this experiment only looked at three of them and then they concluded that.

0:52:6.460 --> 0:52:9.420

Whaley, Paul

They had tested the hypothesis they had shown.

Whaley, Paul

The substance wasn't and.

Whaley, Paul

That's, that's that conclusion. But we know looking at that that you need to test all six and then someone else comes along and tests all six and finds on the other three measures that it is cap toxic and that that first experiment gave a incorrect negative result.

Whaley, Paul

Would that might might that be viewable as an incomplete test of hypothesis? And how would you interpret that in terms of bias? Is it?

Whaley, Paul

To me, that doesn't quite sound like bias, but.

No, not me either. And also like I mean, if you're working with in vitro system, you're knowing that I mean or even if you work with an animal, it's just a model, it's not necessarily what's happening.

So you would not, right? You wouldn't say that it's, you would say it's not hepatotoxic based on these three.

3 experiments or these three endpoints?

I mean, it's doesn't, I don't know. I don't. I don't find it like.

A bias in that sense.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Accepting the finding where they were in this hypothetical example that the researcher said that it wasn't.

Whaley, Paul

And then if another three watches researchers don't do the same three, and then another three, so then you've got three studies of those 3 endpoints.

Whaley, Paul

Finding though that it's not, but they're all in complete studies.

Whaley, Paul

Then he would potentially, I think, have a body of evidence which was underestimating hepatic toxicity. Of that exposure. Is that a lot right?

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

But in but in that context, I would just call it a an error of the interpretation of the data. Basically in on the side of the scientist and not a bias of the of the individual individual systems.

Whaley, Paul

Yep, so this may be better viewed as.

Whaley, Paul

Maybe the issue that the choice of question was getting at more relates to interpretation. Maybe detection bias maybe, maybe even it's it's an indirectness or external auditory issue than it is necessarily choice of question. So think about choice of question here. Might not be particularly helpful. I think that's the feeling I'm getting guru. At this point we want to make that.

Whaley, Paul

When we're getting some mods, OK, very good. So framing of the hypothesis.

Whaley, Paul

Any thoughts on that?

Whaley, Paul

Does that feel like the same thing as incomplete test of hypothesis?

Thing.

Whaley, Paul

Then in relation to selective use of historical contextual data when setting context.

Whaley, Paul

How to do you think odd? Mm hmm.

That's different.

Because that, to me would seem like a bias.

With selective use of the historical and contextual data.

Then you're trying to. I mean hide something or emphasise something.

But I don't know if it if there if it's a choice or question bias, but this is very evaluated.

Maybe it could be proved differently.

Whaley, Paul

Potentially. Yeah. I mean, these were just our best guess at where it belonged based on the information that we had. So you know by the time it's been discussed by 20 people, we'd probably end up making quite some quite different decisions about where we grouped things. So it's certainly possible that it's not optimally grouped.

Whaley, Paul

I guess in terms of thinking about how this might introduce bias, I mean I edit a lot of research, I'm not quite sure I'm clear in my own mind of how I mean, I wouldn't like to see selective presentation of context, right in a the introductory part of a study manuscript, but I'm not sure if I've clear in my own mind as to how that might introduce bias in the results and findings of a study.

Whaley, Paul

Do you have any thoughts on how?

Whaley, Paul

Funny business in the introduction when it comes to his historical contextual data.

Whaley, Paul

Would introduce bias into findings or results?

Whaley, Paul

Or might this be something that we can disregard as not being sufficiently relevant when it comes to understanding bias? When we say doing systematic reviews?

I don't think it's something that sounds important, but sounds like it could introduce a systematic bias.

But I'm really thrilling to think of a specific example where historical data is is is, you know, really used.

In interpreting or setting the context for the vitro essay, it's I'm not, it's nothing really coming to my mind.

The only thing I can think of is the concentration curves.

The If you have.

Faulty or old or concentration curves that have been, yeah, based on something that is not relevant anymore or.

You have used old chemicals. You have gotten the wrong wrong concentration curve, something like that.

Then it would be more.

What do you mean by concentration curve?

Yeah, if you make.

Before you will before you start an experiment to know which concentrations you are measuring, you make a concentration curve so that you will interpolate with with the concentration curve as a basis, and if that's faulty then everything will be wrong. But that's more. It has to do with analysis actually.

And and not choice or question bias.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

So I'm just.

Yeah, but that makes sense.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, that makes sense.

Whaley, Paul

OK. And then?

I guess it's if you frame your question based on your historical data and the historical data was incorrect and you realised that when you are doing your next experiment or your next study and you have to change. But I don't know if that's considered a bias. I mean that would be just something you.

How to do a new experiment right? Then you have to redo.

Hmm.

Hmm.

Right when you may maybe when it fits that with a situation where you think that something is a positive control because some of the literature indicates it and you use it as a positive control or a negative control or whatever in your in your study. But it's actually wrong. But then based on what was in the literature before this is sent biasing your interpretation.

I'm an essay. Could this fit as an idea?

Whaley, Paul

Just can you just say that one again, really, I think I was. I was following you and then wasn't suddenly. So just try that again just so I can respond.

Oh, sorry, you lost me.

Whaley, Paul

I I was thinking very hard and then I realised I was thinking so hard that I'd lost track of what you were saying. So.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Now I was thinking, you know, in what situation could historical architectural data be relevant? And I was thinking of, you know, you have you have some kind of vitro essay where you try to detect.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

If something is, I don't hypothetoxic, for example right and then in order to do that you have your in vitro essay. You measure some response, but then you need to put the response to a context and you have to in the end, you know, call something a positive or a negative and in order to do that you use reference compounds. So positive controls or negative controls and you think.

That based on the historical data published in the literature somewhere, that something should be a positive control.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm mm.

And should be, you know should tell you what response a positive should give you in this essay, but it's actually wrong because the compound has been misclassified in the in the literature in the past, and then you this error perpetuates through.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

The interpretation of your vitro results into the future.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, that sounds so. I think that sounds all like detection bias to me than it is necessarily choice of question bias. So I think maybe this is just probably we could pop this in the wrong place or it's addressing something that doesn't really relate to risk of BI assessment for an vitre study. So I think either way.

Whaley, Paul

I think I'm happy to proceed. Then if we talk about selective harvesting of components of exposure. This also looks like it might be just allocated to the wrong domain.

Whaley, Paul

As it looks to me like some some aspect of selection bias where you're picking out.

I agree.

Whaley, Paul

Maybe exposure components are going to give you a favourable result from a complex mixture or something, I don't know umm or non representative. Yeah, OK, good. Right. Let's move on to the next one. So conflicted interest bias. So just three here.

Whaley, Paul

So this is a bias in which decision makers influencing research design, conduct analysis or reporting have goals or motivations that conflict with scientific research objectives that make sense to you as a biased domain, good.

Whaley, Paul

Not saying this is easy to evaluate in a in vitro context, the two things that.

Whaley, Paul

Were under this domain that seem to be generating challenges for consensus related to sources of funding and then management of interests, I think we only had three items, so we can look at all of them easily. So we've got sources of funding, management of conflicts of interest and absence of pre study agreements distorting results.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

Any thoughts as to why sources of funding might have been challenging to consensus?

Whaley, Paul

Yes.

May I? Yep. I think it's because.

For instance, when you're applying to.

The European Research Council.

And of course, National Research councils, it is expected that you have cooperation with industry.

So it's almost impossible now not to be, so to say, influenced by or or when you're.

Operating them with them. Then you.

Yeah, it may not seem like you're not influenced by their.

By their goals or.

Finances or what they want to achieve?

But it's it's very difficult not to to cooperate with the with the commercial organisations.

Whaley, Paul

I mean that, I guess this might be similar to when we talk about blinding, is that blinding a study might be challenging?

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

But it doesn't mean it's not important, right? So we know, like in surgery research, for example, that it's very obviously very hard to blind somebody as to whether you chop their leg off or not.

Whaley, Paul

If you if you blind the surgeon, the operation tends to not go so well.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

But it still it still has an impact, right? So I think so, maybe the issue here is differentiating the potential source for the bias from the management of the interests, right? So I think you know in some conflict of interest policies, there's, you know, there's tendency to declarations and there's also some that tend towards management. So do you have any sense of why management of conflict of interests might not have achieved consensus?

Whaley, Paul

'Cause, if you think about if you've got a research team, you have, you know, various interests, right, and you're trying to prevent those interests from compromising the study. You'd be looking at managing those. And then you'd then you'd presumably think if you've done a good job that those interests hadn't.

Whaley, Paul

Uh affected the integrity or uh or like sort of damage the project or something in any way? And if you had been less successful managing, you might be more worried about the integrity of the findings. I just mean in the broad sense, not in the someone's a liar sense just in the the the structure of it. Do you have any thoughts as to why maybe that wasn't consensus on that? Do you think it is important, do you think it's maybe not important when it comes to evaluating and Vitra study?

Whaley, Paul

And if you throw it.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

This maybe it's difficult to measure or difficult to know.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

I'm sure it can be difficult, yeah.

I I I think the same. I think it's it's it's of course in in an abstract way important. But practically speaking how I couldn't just couldn't think of the way personally then how how would you evaluate that you know afterwards.

And it's such, yeah. Then I will be.

Whaley, Paul

Well, it's quite so. I think it's not maybe not. So I'm going to so because I I added a lot of stuff, right, so I this is something I'm I'm more familiar territory here is that you can have you can document a researcher can document a process by which they identified and then managed interests, right. So typically you would have a fairly comprehensive accounting of the interests of people involved in the

study be they financial or non financial and then you have a set of policies that you introduce as the π .

Whaley, Paul

Where you say, OK, given the interest we've identified, what we've done is we've removed the this person with these interests from, say, a decision making role in the conduct of the research, right. So they might sit there an advisory capacity, but they might not make decisions. We might make extra effort to to, to mask them if they're doing. If you do decide they can do data analysis. So. But you mask them to the like exposure and groups or something. Right. So there there'll be measures that you could take.

Whaley, Paul

So you'd be more confident that that person's interests because they go in two directions.

Whaley, Paul

Aren't going to compromise the study. We do that a lot in systematic review, right? Because we have people who are who are experts. So one of the ways in which interests can derail a systematic review is if you have people just evaluating their own studies for risk of bias. So what you do is you, you'd have a policy where you'd identify one of the interests you don't have. You don't. Of the studies that are included in the systematic review. And if the answer is yes, then you have a policy where you say that those people can't do the risk bias evaluation job done. Right.

Exactly.

Whaley, Paul

So we like to see these kinds of policies and studies if we possibly can. We just very rarely have any information about it because journals aren't very good at collecting declarations of interest and management of interest policy, right. But in theory, it's very important, right? Yep.

Whaley, Paul

Hmm.

Yeah, yeah. But. But I I think this is probably where the you know difference in evaluation comes from some people's. I mean, yes, in principle it's very important, but practically you just read on like 90% of the papers people saying, yeah, no, no conflict of interest. And then the question is what do you do with it? Do you then say, OK, well, all the ones that don't have an elaborate conflict of interests analysis are potentially biased or, you know, I just, yeah.

I think this.

Whaley, Paul

You might do that in the same way that you know 30 years ago we look at animal studies or, you know, human clinical trials. And we're like, well, nobody here was blinded. That's just a structural issue with the evidence, right? You don't disregard it just because it's not.

Whaley, Paul

Just because you don't know, I mean, you might. You might just be like, well, we just don't know and that's annoying. But he still wouldn't. You wouldn't say it's not important. It's just something you can't really action. So if we so maybe are we saying that it might be important or probably is important? Might be very difficult to get data on.

Whaley, Paul

So maybe the all you end up becomes a poor discriminator, right?

Yeah, but I do think it's important to include. I mean, people should always include if there is any source of funding and conflict of interest, source of funding. I think it's easier in this case than the conflict of interest to, but I think it's important to include.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I agree.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good.

Whaley, Paul

So I think one of the said the absence of pre study agreements distorting results, I think that relates to like a way of 11 strategy and approaching management of conflicts of interest, right. So you have a pre study agreement with the funder for example that they don't have any control over when and where you publish your findings or the you know you publish before they read the manuscript or or various other things you can do to make sure that nothing's gone wrong.

Whaley, Paul

At least in that particular instance, OK.

Whaley, Paul

Good. Get some nods so we can move on to confounding covariant bias so only two items here.

Whaley, Paul

Situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable.

Whaley, Paul

Play.

Whaley, Paul

And then we had two themes for our two items. So one was the other considerations.

Whaley, Paul

And then one was susceptibility to confounding. And then if we look at the specific items that we've got while it's susceptibility to compounding and other considerations, that was very manageable. It wasn't it. So I suspect correct if I'm wrong here, the issue is that in when you're doing controlled.

Whaley, Paul

Like in vitro studies, it's a laboratory experiment, so confound is it less relevant? Obviously, much less relevant in fact.

Whaley, Paul

The only time I think it's compositively relevant would be if you're dealing with primary cell cultures, but I'd be right in thinking that.

Yeah, I think so.

Whaley, Paul

So I think probably we understand what was happening here. I was quite surprised that as much stuff related to confounding was considered to be relevant actually. So these were just a couple of like by hanging bits.

Whaley, Paul
So then Yep.

Whaley, Paul
Mm.

But I mean, I mean I guess it depends what you sort of understand by the term confounding factors, right? I mean, if you think about physical things as like I don't temperature or time of day or something, then you could think of other.

Good thing of other domains as count finding vectors and then they might be relevant.

Whaley, Paul
See those would be.

Whaley, Paul
I think I think the way that we would see that would be that like time of day is part of the exposure profile. So you could have systematic difference in exposure, but confound would be something that is is.

Whaley, Paul
It's something that remains after your sampling strategy, right? So it really relates to population sampling.

Whaley, Paul
We got systematic differences.

Whaley, Paul
Between the oh God, I'm so bad explaining this. Can I send you an explanation by e-mail when I've checked my notes because I am absolutely hopeless explaining confounding, and I always lay myself in trouble when I do it.

Whaley, Paul
I lost.

But what can I like? For example feeding of the cells which I mean 'cause it's related to the day of the time of the day. Could that would that be considered a Co funding because some measurements?

Will be masked if the cells have just been fed because.

They're their metabolism is just like going over the roof.

Whaley, Paul
So I so I'll just pulled up my my good epidemiologist's friend's explanation of confounding fellow was going to try to say they say confounding exists in the population before the study occurs.

OK, good form.

OK.

Whaley, Paul
Umm, so if you you're introducing it through the conductor study, that's a different type of bias. Uh. So lots of things strictly are sort of confounders, but I think confounding here because it was kind of came from the observational.

Whaley, Paul

Of instruments for assessing risk of arson, observational studies was about population characteristics prior to.

Whaley, Paul

Starting the study and then there's I've got, yeah.

I think that explains also the the different responses of people to the items.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, of course. Yeah. Yeah, yeah, absolutely. But it's quite hard to understand. It was kind of an odd thing to throw. We kind of had to throw it in because, you know, the the way that we'd include a different sizing, we didn't want to inadvertently exclude stuff for kind of niche in vitre study designs. So probably this would certainly have to be taken care of in a in a study with primary cell cultures potentially, but probably not in a in a.

Whaley, Paul

In a laboratory kind of experimental setup. So why you're just using uh, cell lines and things.

Whaley, Paul

But maybe even then, I don't know, we'd have to see.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

I don't know. Could be like if you make like a stomach, iip S induced proportion stem cells, for example, and your using different.

Different lines for you know that are.

Genetically modified, for example, and they have been done made differently. That could be something that are should be considered.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm. OK, that's like that.

Whaley, Paul

Was gonna make that hurt.

Whaley, Paul

Right. So then we've got 11 minutes left, so we won't get the whole way through just action bias, 'cause, there's 42 items in there.

Whaley, Paul

Easily one of the more complicated.

Whaley, Paul

Domains, so this is a bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable. Does that make sense to you?

Whaley, Paul

So it's very broad.

Whaley, Paul

Side things that were seem to be challenging.

Whaley, Paul

So we had this idea of masking of investigators who are taking measurements.

Whaley, Paul

There were issues around latency, lead in and watch out periods for.

Whaley, Paul

I guess that's if you've got cells, how long it takes for them to develop the outcome that you're interested in.

Whaley, Paul

How long it takes, I guess abatement will be part of this. So how long it takes for that to disappear depending on your, your, your experiment and then I think washout may more apply to people.

Whaley, Paul

When you're being confident that they're no longer exposed to the exposure, but maybe that's important as well.

Whaley, Paul

Variables used for measuring confounding. So our friend, confounding comes up again here in a different domain.

Whaley, Paul

Extent to which the applied exposure matches the exposure of interest.

Whaley, Paul

And then data categorization and threshold values that may actually take us back to our dichotomization issue, of course.

Whaley, Paul

So any thoughts on any of these at this stage has to buy or how these might of course issues if there may be in the wrong place if I don't understand any thoughts at all.

I think they all seem highly relevant.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Whaley, Paul

Not scared, OK, so we can look at some specific examples.

Whaley, Paul

So a choice of metric for exposure.

Whaley, Paul

That was no consensus on that. I'm just wondering why you think that might be or if you think it's obviously important or if you think it's obviously unimportant.

I mean it, it has to be. It has to be.

Defined.

But whether you use one sort of metric or another, as long as you say what you're doing.

I mean it's you cannot not report metric.

So.

Yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm, but can you have the wrong one? I mean, it seems I mean I'm naive, but it seems to me very possible. You could choose the wrong metric. I'm just trying to think of.

Yeah.

But but if you're trying to, it's more like if you're trying to use a metric so that you get higher values. So and you hope that people with will not notice. I mean, but that's also in the line of cheating.

I don't. I'm not sure how it's related to bias.

OK.

Hey there, I don't really get it because I mean, as long as you're explaining what metric you're using, isn't that enough?

Can I? Can I ask what you understand by metric of exposure?

But also we have us potentially.

Whaley, Paul

For me, I was hoping you'd tell me what you understand by it.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Because, I mean, I I I think of something like, you know what? You provide a nominal concentration or a a maximum concentration that you when you look at the the AUC like really the exposure over time.

But.

Is that what you interpreted by this?

Whaley, Paul

Well, what I interpret doesn't matter because we're the whole point of this exercise is we find out what's on, I think. But I can tell you how I would interpret this for outcome. Right, 'cause. There's something I'm all familiar with. So if you imagine that you're working with people and you are have a metric for outcome. So you're looking at, say, the effect of, say, PFAS exposure on intelligence and then you use IQ as your metric for outcome and you measure people's IQ and you use that for intelligence.

Whaley, Paul

It might be that.

Whaley, Paul

IQ doesn't discriminate very well. Say it.

Whaley, Paul

Well enough. Maybe it doesn't discriminate very well. Maybe at certain ranges we're expecting P fast to have an effect, like if maybe let's imagine P fast has more effect on people with lower IQ than average IQ and.

Whaley, Paul

An IQ test is worse at discriminating at lower levels.

Whaley, Paul

Of course, at low levels of IQ or something, so it's not very good at discriminating in the range at which you'd expect P fast to have an effect.

Whaley, Paul

Then maybe someone will say, well, your choice of metric for outcome there is not really very ideal for what it is you're actually trying to measure, and it should use a different.

Whaley, Paul

Metric for intelligence like some, I don't know, maybe spatial reasoning or.

Whaley, Paul

Verbal skills or I don't? I have no idea. Mathematical. You know, it's just something that's like a less general test than IQ. That's better. Just for the purposes of using it.

Whaley, Paul

I don't know about exposure metrics in vitro though.

Well, that's not how I thought about it. I thought about it's just how you measure the exposure, which is would be the exposure you're putting into your well. But if you're thinking about the outcome as the metric for it.

Whaley, Paul

No, no. This is about exposure. Specifically, I just was talking about outcomes to give an example I could think of.

Whaley, Paul

Would it be that?

Whaley, Paul

I mean, I guess is it like you're probably trying to figure out what the?

Whaley, Paul

'Cause presume there's a difference between the amount of stuff you put in the well and what the equivalent of internal explanation would be, right?

Whaley, Paul

So when we're doing stuff in people, there's quite a lot of quite complicated, biokinetic transformations we have to do right to figure out what the exposure in the liver is, or the brain or something, because you can tell how much you've put in the person. But it it it's, you know, frowned upon to start taking brain samples from people to find out what their internal exposure is in the old grey matter. So you have to model it. But I'm just wondering if you're, like, looking at maybe biomarkers.

Whaley, Paul

As your magic for exposure, so you're not directly measuring, would that be something that can lead to an an error in?

Whaley, Paul

Measurement of what the actual exposure is and can that happen in vitro in some way?

But I think we mainly measure the concentration of the compound. That's how we measure it normally and you can do it, yes, within the cells and that could potentially be.

Some kind of a bias, but most of the people do not do that because it's time consuming and we should. But we're just looking at the nominal concentration that we put in the well in general that I think what you will get in the majority of the studies and that's why I mean it's not, you know what you're putting in to your well. It doesn't matter if you're.

Describing it as.

You know.

Whaley, Paul

But if so, what we need to do is we need to differentiate between what people normally do versus what they should do, right, so.

Whaley, Paul

If nominal concentration is not a good matchup for exposure, then we should know that right? Even if it's something that everybody does, so is it possible that on a even if it's just on occasions that someone giving exposure in terms of normal concentration?

Whaley, Paul

Is actually a MIS measurement of exposure to the point where detection bias might start becoming an issue, and you'd be like, no, no, we need to design these these assays differently or we need to do a different explosion measurement in order to understand what's actually going on here in terms of exposure.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Thinking about it like this, blinding surgeons again, we know that we can't do it, but we have to remember.

I I really think so. I really think that's important. It's important when you think about it in terms of space. You know, so is, is it just the nominal concentration in the medium or is it really intracellularly or even in?

You know some sub silly like apartment, but also over time is it is it, you know volatile is it being degraded in the in vitro system and therefore the concentration is going down over time. But I think probably the reason why there's A and I'm sure there is there is a bunch of people thinking that's important.

To consider, but I guess then also some people said well. But practically speaking, we just work with phenomenal concentration and that's just then at least consistent you know throughout what people are doing and therefore maybe they rated this is a less important item.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So what we're trying to do here is ignore practicality and just understand like it's theoretical impact cause research practise change quite significantly over time. Usually when we figured out we're doing something sub optimally. So at this stage we want a a really good understanding of whether or not.

Whaley, Paul

An approach is suboptimal and distinguish that from whether or not the ideal approach is practical.

Whaley, Paul

And that's why we're trying to, yeah.

Hmm.

Well, then I would say it is important, especially for certain chemicals like P FAS for example, just throw throwing out one example there. It's extremely important to understand because it's binding. So many things are binding to plastic and it's very sticky and the cells won't actually see what you're putting in the media.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

For priority of them, but.

Good luck with.

Yes, I can also think of several things now that I had the chance to think about it a little because as a reviewer I also.

Always.

Comment on on on how things are are measured in. So in my field it would be. For instance, the distance from irradiation to to the cell's surface.

It's it's of very big importance and and also when they use non standardised.

Units there is also difference between the United States and and the Europe for for different ways of measuring radiation. So that could be, yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good.

Whaley, Paul

Solved.

Change my mind.

Whaley, Paul

Well, we're at half past now, so we're going to stop here and thank you for your time and interest and very enthusiastic discussion of something. It's very difficult. It can be quite frustrating for people. So your patience is hugely appreciated and obviously your expertise and thank you so much. We will run the next two and then report back to you as to how things have gone and if we have any remaining questions, I think hopefully not, but we shall see.

Great. Thank you very much.

Whaley, Paul

Good. Well, thank you.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

Yeah.

But I would say I hope because I thought this was fun. Now we got into the the interesting.

Whaley, Paul

It is fun, isn't it? It's like I really like this stuff.

It takes it it takes some time to warm up to it, but then it's fun.

Whaley, Paul

It is. It is tough and it does require some warm up time and I think all this stuff is super interesting, but I'm quite a special case I think sometimes but.

Well, thank you.

Workshop 13.05.2024

Whaley, Paul

So starting with detection bias, so we had 42 items here.

Whaley, Paul

Defined as a bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable. OK, bit of a mouthful.

Whaley, Paul

So the themes that came through from the Delphi process.

Whaley, Paul

Related to the masking investigators taking measurements in the study.

Whaley, Paul

Issues relating to latency lead in and washout periods.

Whaley, Paul

For the experiment with the exposure, I think.

Whaley, Paul

Variables that we used for measuring confounding, the extent to which the applied exposure matches the exposure of interest.

Whaley, Paul

And takes a categorization and threshold values. OK, so does anyone have any questions at this point before I show you specific items like this? Rings any bells you have? Any comments that you want to make?

Could you briefly describe the decency leading and washout periods want to make sure we are all on the same page.

Whaley, Paul

Yes. So as I understand it, and again, this isn't just to emphasise, this isn't necessarily for me to understand. We had a whole load of stuff in a bucket, right? And it's not necessarily the case that we understood it either. We were just capturing concepts as best we could from the literature and from the.

Whaley, Paul

Focus groups, but I think latency is the time between the exposure and the outcome manifesting.

Whaley, Paul

Lead in is I think similar and then.

Whaley, Paul

Wash out is how long it takes for an exposure to zero out again after it stops being administered. I think washout is typically used more in epidemiological studies where you're interested in how long it takes for people to stop being exposed to a substance they've been exposed to once the exposure stops.

I have also a question if I may.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm, of course.

See. See I I don't understand really if the variables use for measuring confounding.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yes, that's a complicated one. So one of the tools that we included in our literature review was Robin's E, which is a risk of bias assessment instrument for observational studies. The reason we included Robin Z is that there's good reason for thinking that many of the concepts relating to bias or what can introduce bias into a study are generalizable across all study designs. So it doesn't really matter if it's in vitro or observational.

Whaley, Paul

When you've got a modern by one of the very most recently developed tools.

Whaley, Paul

There's ways of thinking about interrogating potential for bias in those tools that don't exist in the older in vitro specific tools, so these concepts of confounding have come through from tools like that, and I think.

Yes, that I know, I know. Therefore, I'm asking. Yeah. Why do you think that it is?

Applicable also for this in vitro situation.

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

We don't necessarily. The Delphi process didn't achieve consensus on this item, right. So our process was to identify all the items and concepts, put those to Delphi, and then what happened in the Delphi is that there was some people who thought it should be in and some people who thought it should be out.

Whaley, Paul

But there wasn't consensus.

Mm hmm mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Which is interesting.

Hmm.

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

So what we're trying to do today is just to clarify what direction that consensus should go in.

Mm hmm mm hmm.

Mm.

Whaley, Paul

What I might do is I just bumpers onto the next slide so you can see the specific items that are remaining here. So Group One was already able to help us identify that the choice of metric for explosion should be in because that was one of the ones that was uncertain and no longer is.

Whaley, Paul

So we've got this latency period for outcome knowledge, but maybe if we move straight onto 185, which is validity of variables used for measurement of confounders.

Whaley, Paul

One of the proposals here has been that.

Whaley, Paul

Confounding.

Yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Doesn't really matter for experimental studies, right? At least it shouldn't.

Whaley, Paul

But there might be circumstances in when you're doing in vitro type methods where you're using primary biological samples from people that are using the in vitro methods to study the people, in which case confounding may become important.

Yeah, but then it is a selection of the people.

Whaley, Paul

Indeed.

Yeah, it's in me to study.

Whaley, Paul

Well, it might be difficult to see where the line is when you're assessing for risk of bias, right?

Yeah. Yeah. OK. Yeah, yeah, yeah, yeah, yeah, that is. That is perhaps it should be good explained. So that people know about. Yeah, that is Special Situations that you have. You have specimen fun from patients or healthy subjects. You you look in vitro for it's it's it's a point. Yeah.

Special. Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. I mean one thing we might consider doing when we develop the invites in uh, tool is making it a modular tool. So we have like a kind of a source tool which is for just kind of regular in vitro studies and then there will be a module for studies of primary biological samples and we might we might be tempted to not make that module in the first version of invites in.

Whaley, Paul

Could be very complicated.

Whaley, Paul

Might need a different method for getting to grips with all of the confounding issues and other issues that may be important for that particular study type.

Second idea of the different modules. Some of the things, particularly on the exposure part of nanomaterial research, is its own category, different from most.

That can be lumped together with any particles nouns.

Anything that doesn't dissolve might have its own category versus the ones that they solve.

Whaley, Paul

It's good point. So I agree. If we captured that, so it says no nano materials, it's the distinction of dissolving and non dissolving non soluble exposures I guess.

Whaley, Paul

So that gives us 2 modules.

Whaley, Paul

Good. So how does? Oh, yes, yes.

Oh, can I? Can I ask? Sorry. Yes. Would you like to have comments on this now or would you will you start the discussion some other way? I'm not quite sure if you would like to.

Get feedback on this specific items right now or not. Yeah, OK.

Yes, I know.

Whaley, Paul

Yes, please. Yes. Oh, sorry. I'm afraid I completely overlooked you. 'cause. You're invisible in my team space. You were hiding under my recording side. So I'm sorry about that.

So my comment is for the first time item related to here, this is not really something that is expressed like this for in vitro studies. But of course the time point between the exposure and the measurement, I don't time point is something to consider, but it's not usually called latency. That's why this is.

Probably been a bit confusing to get agreement on.

But if that is meant and then this is relevant. But but could be formulated in other way, the time time between exposure and measurement is of course something that should be assessed.

Whaley, Paul

Yes.

And and my mm hmm.

And my comment on the second one, because this is related to if the if the individual who is doing the outcome assessment is aware of about exposure for that specific cell or well in, in a cell assay and of course this is really relevant for indivo animal studies, but.

As as in my experience, this is not really the most difficult studies, this is not applicable because most in vitro measurements.

Are done more as automatically and then I should be the individual is not really involved in that, but then that this is not applicable. But if you're if you're considering to have different types of of, combine this in different types of tools, then of course there could be some in vitro tools when when this could be relevant, but for many it's not. This is important to that may be the reason for there's not so much consensus on this one.

Whaley, Paul

Could well be Yep.

So that was my comment on that phone. Yeah, alright. I know next one then we already discussed this about confounders and of course confounders is not something that you usually consider in vitro studies and or even if you have like samples from different patients or individuals and you take the self from them and then reduce that then.

I'm not sure if confounders is still the correct way of expressing that, but then of course one has to take into consideration any variability between the different samples.

And in that case, for different patients, individuals, but it may be not confounders, some may be some other expression that will be used there.

So that has to be clarified in. That's in that if that is included.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

And then about exposure, I mean it's a mostly victor studies of course any I think that you already expressed this about the exposure of particles, nanomaterials and for the for exposure data studies. Of course it is. We usually consider what is actually added to like the cell cell medium and what is the internal.

Levels in the cells that is usually not.

I tell them they measured, so that is maybe something to be taken to into account. Otherwise you would just consider that the the substance added to the sale medium is the exposure that is considered and in that sense this is not maybe so relevant except in those cases they may measure the intracellular concentration of the chemical or the particle.

M.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I think just holding on to item 200 for a bit 'cause, I think this is one of the trickier ones that we'd trying to get to grips with. So when I look at this, part of me thinks that we need to make a distinction between.

Whaley, Paul

The applied exposure.

Whaley, Paul

Matching the exposure that was intended to be applied, right? So you can try to apply one unit and accidentally only apply half a unit of exposure or two units of exposure, right?

Whaley, Paul

So I'm actually like nano materials, maybe that don't dissolve, you could end up underexposing quite significantly.

Whaley, Paul

But the than than the difference between how whether the extent to which the explosion is given matches the exposure of interest, feels like an issue of.

Whaley, Paul

Applicability or external literacy of the study. Right, because you can the study can give a true result for the.

Whaley, Paul

The fact that the given exposure had the question of whether or not the given exposure is relevant to the question you're trying to answer is may be different. So I'm wondering if maybe what's happened in this item is that these some of the lack of clarity has come from the item kind of blurring the boundary between or being unclear as to whether or not it's an issue of applicability or external validity, and whether or not it's an issue of internal registry or bias.

Whaley, Paul

Is that like any sense to anybody?

Hmm.

And.

You.

I think it's it's the term measured exposure that maybe is not really applicable to in vitro because in many cases you don't actually measure the exposure the same way as you would do in in epidemiological study for example. So neither in vivo, in vivo or in vivo. So I think that is the term that is not so clear for in vitro, that's why it's been difficult to understand what this is meant. But the artist actually mentioned there are different actual amount to the substance you add to to the cell medium and then there is might be.

Part of that substance is actually not taking up the cells. It's sticking to the plastic or and then and then and then what is actually internal concentration that you should not mention so so exposure is relevant, but maybe the way to express here it makes it difficult to really. Yeah. To capture that.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So maybe there's two issues then. So in the first instance, if we changed the term measured exposure to applied exposure.

Whaley, Paul

Would that suddenly make this make more sense just to get a sense?

Since no, since the term you, you, you have to use is phenomenal exposure, that is the nominal concentration and the other if you measure that it is the actual concentration and there are people around who measures the content of the substance or the particles in in the cell.

The actual yeah, yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

OK. So then we have 3 clarifications. So there is the uh nominal versus the. Sorry, Participant, what was the actual he said the actual Yep. So normal versus actual.

Whaley, Paul

Applied exposure characterising exposure of interest and the issue of.

Whaley, Paul

This uh being ambiguous between external literacy and uh, internal literacy, I think we're just gonna ask other people.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

The Internet is the actual the nominal is is the outside, the concentration you add to this to the.

To the to the suspension for example, and not.

It's not very often measured.

Whaley, Paul

Indeed, yes. So we heard this on the previous group as well, so.

There are only a few, a few articles you can find to show whether they have measured that into the sales pension and also.

I I know some of the papers and I I was also not sure what you mean with the measured exposures and I have given the interpretation that it was the actual concentration.

But I said.

Whaley, Paul

Yes, I mean it could be in terms of I think the issue with some of these items is that it's just, you know from the contacts in which they were used and the way that we abstracted the item from the tool that then or from the focus group discussion, then it's not necessarily clear exactly what it means. So the purpose of this discussion is to provide some of that clarity and understand where the ambiguity is so we can resolve it right.

Yeah. Yeah, yeah, yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. And I did. So I think we should just turn to some other people.

What do you mean with exposure of interest? That is also not very clear.

Whaley, Paul

So the exposure of interest is.

Whaley, Paul
Presumably the.

Whaley, Paul
Real world exposure that the in vitro study is intended to be informative of right.

So in in vitro.

Yeah, OK. Yeah.

One of the case might be that you have an undefined mixture is your interest, but when you do the experiments, you pick a composite.

Composition of the mixture to test so that becomes different. Your actual administer exposure becomes different from your exposure of interest.

Whaley, Paul
It so I think.

Yes. Yes, I yeah, I agree with both of those maybe on this. So I think that's three different types of exposure we have the normal exposure, that is what we intend to add to the cell medium and then then the next one is is actually what is actually concentration in in the cell medium because some, some, some.

Yeah. And what is it intercellularly you have also to look what is in the cell. Yeah, yeah.

Mm hmm. Mm hmm mm hmm mm.

Yes, exactly those. That's rest, right? Yes, those three are different concentrations that and I usually when we when we look at them to those response relationship, we need to study, we consider the nominal exposure what you added but actually it might be in some cases it's actually that that concentration that's not reached into the cells where it's as can affect the function. So this can be captured but but but the terms in this one 200 doesn't really yeah capture this but these are the important things to be captured I think.

Yeah, yeah.

Oh, I would suggest that we use a different term for internal concentration in instead of internal exposure to separate. That's the result.

Now in AD and E discussions, they don't talk about internal exposures. They take talk about uptake and.

Those kind of things, perhaps that will.

It will make it easier to distinguish.

What's considered exposure versus in the cells?

And the the exposure of interest, you can only find out if you do it in in Weaver extrapolation. Otherwise you don't know.

Whaley, Paul
Right. So I'm gonna suggest we move on to the next item. I think we've got from our purposes here, we have plenty to be going on to help resolve this and then any further clarification we can do through the next phase of the study.

Whaley, Paul

So next item is the differences in measurement of outcome between exposure levels. So this is.

Whaley, Paul

The thing this is an instance where you might use a different measurement for a higher exposure versus a lower exposure level.

Whaley, Paul

This happens sometimes. Observational research. Is there any analogue in in vitro research?

Whaley, Paul

Or is it not applicable?

I if yeah, if I comment OK if if this is the way you sign. If you don't know, because I think I would say that in vitro research this is not the case you have you have.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Your cells or whatever exposed and then you use the same type of measurement for all of them. Otherwise it would not be. It wouldn't be in the same experiments. Do different types of. Yeah for high or low doses. So. So I don't think that that's why don't if it's if that is the meant by this one. I don't think it's relevant for in vitro.

Whaley, Paul

Suspect. So Participant, do you have any, do you agree?

Yeah, I agree. Because I remember I was quite confused because I wasn't quite sure what was meant with the differences in measurement, because I I wasn't sure if it was referring to different methods or whatever. But yeah, I think I can't think of ever using different methods to measure high or low or anything because then it makes interpretation not very useful. So.

Whaley, Paul

Indeed.

I wouldn't say it's particularly helpful.

I agree with you. Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

OK, so we can potentially, I mean obviously if this happened, it would be quite important. But if there's if it's so unlikely that we don't need to think about it, then maybe we can eliminate it.

Whaley, Paul

I think it's generally considered not to be a great situation to be in with an observational study, but sometimes you're stuck with the data collection methods you have available or say so. Then finally, if we move on to 2021, so we've got typo there detection bars definition of threshold values for data categories.

Whaley, Paul

So this didn't achieve consensus.

Understand that one.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm, so I think I think this is about categorising continuous data, right? So you've got a continuous data range of zero to 100.

Whaley, Paul

And you can say a positive response is a value over 55 and a negative response is a value below 54 or less.

Whaley, Paul

And those that categorisation might be so a way in which bias can be introduced into a study if it's in the wrong place.

Whaley, Paul

Or to find in a funny way, or oversimplifies or does something strange to the data when you come to analyse it.

Whaley, Paul

That was really, that was all there was to it, I think.

Whaley, Paul

'Cause I don't have any thoughts or comments on that. I think and that's we start with you 'cause uh, we're starting with you.

I think it does introduce a bias like that, but that's on based on the interpretation of the data. So I feel if if the.

Fraud data measurements are attached. Then you know that wouldn't be such a big problem.

Mm.

Whaley, Paul

It could be, I mean, the study's still biased. I mean, you might have the raw data to reanalyze later, and then you'd be able to prove the study was biased, right? And then you'd be, well, at least they gave us the raw data, so we don't have to use their interpretation.

Yeah. Yeah, exactly.

Whaley, Paul

So it does still. It feels like to me like an easily diagnosable issue that could easily be fixed later by a systematic reviewer if they were doing a broad data re analysis or something. But it could also still be a bias in the wrong circumstances.

Yeah, if you don't have the data with them. Mm hmm.

Even with the data, most of the systematic review process don't go into re analyse the raw data.

I feel this is extremely difficult to detect.

Because you are, you have basically rerun the data analyzer for every study. If you're doing it.

The data analyses part.

Most of the time the in visual studies have already developed protocols already established thresholds for.

For calling the data positive, negative.

I personally don't think this is one that will happen very often.

Whaley, Paul

Do you mean it won't be a bias very often, or you think that it won't be detectable very often? I mean.

For both of them.

Whaley, Paul

Both of them.

Yeah.

Well, I guess depends on how important that study is for your systematic review. There are very few people who actually go do the analyse again.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I don't think people tend to do the reanalysis very often, personally.

Whaley, Paul

And my personal experience of this as an editor is that I I don't like it when people categorise continuous data.

Whaley, Paul

It makes me very nervous.

Whaley, Paul

Umm.

Whaley, Paul

Stop principle.

If I comment it like.

But I'm not quite sure that's right.

Whaley, Paul

Go ahead.

OK, right. So in some OCD test test guidelines, there are folks in vitro test guidelines, for example, think about test for assays in, in the guideline there are like patient type of values for different categories like positive, negative and and and in between when you can't decide. And of course these these kind of threshold values are important that they are correctly set. So if they are not then that could of course yes. So it could be a bias. I think this way if we if we if we consider this as this type of decision on where the cut off or facial value should be.

To for the decision making, this could be important, I think to be included to include.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I imagine that if you're depending on the.

Whaley, Paul

Distribution of your data where you set the threshold value for categorization could massively affect the detection rate right for your outcome I would presume.

Whaley, Paul

But it wouldn't take much to increase the number of positive outcomes by by or 10%. By nudging your thresholds.

Whaley, Paul

Little bit to the left, right.

Right. And in this?

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Data contest guidelines, then. This has been set to certain value and then of course there's some some decision making behind that. So I suppose this is if also if you think about research data.

If researchers set their own values, of course it could be a reason for for bias, depending on how they what are the criteria for setting the thresholds. That's why I think this could be important to include, but maybe yeah, we explain it or formulate in different ways. It's easier to to understand how this can be used for in virtual.

Whaley, Paul

So yeah, so have No Fear, we won't just be throwing a big bag of very elliptical concepts of people when it comes to them having to use our tool. That would be a most unfair.

I think one thing that I'm just thinking of when I'm reading this is that not all data categories are equally, well, important. This may be the wrong word here, but you know, if you're categorising, say the the main outcome, that's maybe very, you know, throws in a lot of bias or potentially the outcome of a study. But you know, if you think about other categorizations, if you're thinking about, for example, you're using, you know.

I don't know the age of participants. Maybe that's not so critical if you include plus 65 or you know where you put the band of the ageing of the participants when you're collecting the samples.

If maybe not so critical, I mean it all depends on the setup of an experiment, but I do think that the primary outcomes are maybe there. It's a bit more critical.

Yeah.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Good, I think it might depend on the study. I mean, it's funny you should choose ageing. If I was going to mess around with epidemiological data, I would definitely start with the age of.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

Yeah, of course. In in, in episode is. But I'm just thinking, for example, if you're collecting primary, you know, primary sales from people, you know, if you say that you're collecting, you know, the adults, if you set that range up till 60 or 65 or you know it it sometimes it really depends on the setup of your experiment. But yeah, I'm just saying that, you know, if you're a dependent depending, it could be that the primary outcome, if that is you know, is it, you know positive or negative outcome or you know there it's maybe more critical than some other aspects within an experiment.

Whaley, Paul
Yeah, obviously agree.

Or, you know, defining high and low or something, you know? Yeah.

Whaley, Paul
It would be very, I mean it's one of these really interesting things to be to try to understand when and where it matters.

I'm.

Whaley, Paul
Good. OK. So we will, we'll process this into the next into the draught tool. I think this is gonna be really quite a challenging 1 actually to explain properly and make sense.

I'm unsure whether the word definition is the right one.

It is.

Yeah. Yeah. OK. OK. Yeah, OK, good.

Whaley, Paul
It probably isn't. We don't need to worry too much about where smithing in detail at this point, yeah.

Whaley, Paul
We'll come up with something that will be people can meaningfully review, I think.

Whaley, Paul
So we had this massive bias term, which was kind of a catch all that we used for things that we found so confusing. We couldn't put them in a biased domain.

Whaley, Paul
So it's not very surprising to us that quite a few of these, it was quite difficult to get consensus on because we we had this catch all concept. So this meta bias concept was just like a general distorting influence on investigative decision making that may bias the results or findings of the study. So rather open we had 14 items in this.

Whaley, Paul
Domain where we didn't hit consensus.

Whaley, Paul
There seem to be 3 themes within Master Bi, so we had theme an issue around. Investigate the knowledge of exposure status.

Whaley, Paul
The possibility that many of the meta bias issues are actually performance bias. I think looking back is it and reflecting on the comments from the Delphi participants. And then there was an issue of knowledge of data.

Whaley, Paul
Before planning any data analysis.

Whaley, Paul
So.

Whaley, Paul

I think maybe we just should have a quick discussion about each of these in turn before we look at the specific items.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

It was not clear how people viewed the importance of investigator knowledge of exposure status of the samples in relation to the potential for introduction of bias, so this is generally considered to be important in relation to performance bias, probably because knowing whether or not a given certainly in animal study, animal studies and in.

Whaley, Paul

Human trials.

Whaley, Paul

If the investigator knows which arm of the study the subject is in, then we've got good evidence that that affects their perception of how much affects the exposure or treatment is having.

Whaley, Paul

It was less clear how much consensus there was on this the application of this idea to in vitro context, so I don't know if any of you want to explain why you think it's maybe less important or more important, depending on which way you felt feel it should go. Maybe if we start, I mean Participant, we've not really heard from you yet, so maybe I'll put you on the spot.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Well, we are talking about about blinding here or because this is not like it sounds to me. If the investigator knows the groups.

Is performing the treatments or not? Is is this?

Whaley, Paul

So blinding is 1.

Whaley, Paul

Method that you can use to prevent the investigation knowing the exposure status of the.

Whaley, Paul

Of the.

Whaley, Paul

Sample or participant right subject so you can go through a process of random allocation, allocation, concealment. So the investigators that that's before blinding allocation concealment and then after you've got everything into the study.

Whaley, Paul

Then you would have like you know the the exposure being administered is made to look identical whether or not the subject is in the control arm or the one of the exposure arms. And the samples look the same.

Whaley, Paul

And that they have referred to by randomly generated codes instead of like you know, interventional ARM sample one or something like that and various other things to make sure that the investigator doesn't know.

Whaley, Paul

Whether or not the particular sample or plate or whatever it is they're dealing with.

Whaley, Paul

Is in, is in which exposure group. Does that make sense?

Yeah, but yeah, as someone performing experiments, I mean it's it's hard for me to imagine that.

Any research group can control to all of.

This.

Exposure to knowledge about the the research being conducted, you know.

To me it looks like if blinding.

During treatment is is performant then most of these concerns.

I wouldn't say I solved, but you know I minimise it at least.

Whaley, Paul

So would you say you would feel better about the study where the investigators had been blinded?

Yeah, regarding to treatments, yes.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. OK, very good. That's kinda what we'll need to was. Participant, were you wanting to comment?

No, I I agree with that. I think it is just often the reality that with in virtual work teams are maybe smaller and less possibility for blinding, but obviously that's a complete different discussion here.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

But obviously, yeah, I mean it would be ideal to blind as much as possible.

Yeah, technical sets that.

The reality is that the studies are done by 1, two or two people and it's having a team to do the blinding. It's rather difficult when you consider doing any experiment on 96 well plate unless you have robot arms. The blinding makes the chance of making mistakes much higher than any of the bias that you can introduce.

And I think for individual studies, we typically well, my experience is that investigator knows the exposure status.

That's how you run the experiment.

There's there's.

A complexity of the the study design and the performance to consider when you try to blind and randomise things.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Yeah, I agree that this is the reality. What I'm trying to say is that there's is, to me the most important one to be.

Informed.

I understand that.

A significant part may most of the students blind would not be.

Possibility is always.

It is always there but.

The the the consequence or the way the study will be performed.

Blinding will not happen, will not be possible, but this is something that must be declared and and taking a joke out in the in the tool like this.

But yeah, in small groups and small experiment like you you.

6 warplane or something like that, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So I think one of the things we're trying to.

Whaley, Paul

So distinguish or put daylight between and. This is the how easy it is to prevent the bias and what effect.

Whaley, Paul

Preventing the bias would have and keep those two things separate, right? So we know that, like in surgical research in humans, it's very difficult to blind the surgeons.

Whaley, Paul

To the intervention that's being administered because you know when you're chopping off somebody's leg, it's pretty obvious you're chopping off somebody's leg. And if you blind a surgeon, then you know, it's generally not very good for the patient.

Whaley, Paul

But we also know that blinding still matters in surgical research.

Whaley, Paul

Even if you can't really do it right, so you have to accept that there are going to be some necessary limitations on surgical studies. So, Participant, I guess the question for you is even if it is very difficult and very rare for in vitro research groups to blind their studies, would you feel better about their studies if they had been able to do so?

Whaley, Paul

OK. So notwithstanding the.

Not necessarily, because no, you are introducing a lot more complexity and details on this performance so.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, so keeping those dependencies separate, supposing that they had a mechanism by which they could successfully blind and still do their study properly, right, would you feel better?

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Yes.

Yes, I'm concerned about the implication of making all of the in vitro studies.

Inferior than the other types that it though.

Whaley, Paul

That's I think we need to treat those as separate.

I agree.

I agree.

Whaley, Paul

Challenges again, surgical research is not inferior. It's just harder, right?

Whaley, Paul

Depending on your view of sergeants as researchers, let's not ask any doctors.

Whaley, Paul

OK. So we will. So what we will do is we'll approach this obviously very cautiously and carefully, but.

Whaley, Paul

I think I think we know which direction we're going in on this now. So then the final issue is about the importance of or the potential impact of knowing what your data is.

Whaley, Paul

Whilst developing your data analysis plan, right? So the concern here is that if you already know or have already seen the data you intend to analyse.

Whaley, Paul

That you will then that this could increase the risk that the investigators would develop their analysis plans for the shape of the data and thereby be more likely to get the results that they or the findings that they wanted to see, right. So the argument is it would be better if the analysis plan was developed prior to data collection to reduce the risk of that happening. It's a little bit analogous to, say, overfitting.

Whaley, Paul

A logistic regression or machine learning model to data, right?

Whaley, Paul

Just seen too much of it. It's overtrained on that. It gets the convenient result rather than the true result. Does this make any sense to any of you as a?

Whaley, Paul

Those in the space or concept?

It's it's a. It's a very important point. I think that is most important.

And to yeah, it's you can do with the data if you if you change the the analysis what you want to to say.

I I think it's it it it it it?

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. Does anyone else have any thoughts or comments on this?

Well, it's it's challenging again.

I mean.

Again 123.

People working on a on a on the same project usually.

Yeah, can have an. It's difficult to keep such a small group.

Planning the analysis.

Without any knowledge about the data before this analysis, you can you can draught an analysis plan, but.

It's obviously important, but thinking about that, the real world in terms of the labs, I think it's it's really difficult.

To access this in a in a tool like this and to capture the information from the groups and.

And actually.

Take this into account in and not do like this.

Whaley, Paul

It might be. I mean, maybe one of the things and again, just distinguishing importance from practicality like it might be the the first step in or the first use of a tool like this is not to just criticise everybody's research, but you can see where there might be systemic issues in how research is done and then that can lead to change in research practise which can be constructive for the field at large, like when risk of bias tools were first introduced into medical research.

Whaley, Paul

People didn't like them very much because it made everybody's research look bad and everyone felt bad. That wasn't really the point. But then you started seeing once these issues with structural issues in research have been identified that then people started changing their research practises, right? So blinding started becoming very important because we realised, do the tools that we were under blinding our studies, you see. So it might be that, you know, in the short term, like, things look at not potentially great compared to how they could be, but then we can introduce techniques like.

All right.

Whaley, Paul

Pre registration of analysis plans in the same way that clinical trials will have to pre register their analysis plans now, they didn't have to use to, but they'll have to do it legally right in Europe and the US, so there might just be things like that. So again, I think it's about, you know, if we're careful about selling it and telling people how to interpret it and not to be mean.

Whaley, Paul
Could be helpful.

Yeah, I yeah, I agree 100% with you and and.

Many.

Approaches.

Are wonderful and.

Like you mentioned, whining and preregistration. Of course my role here is to try to.

Whaley, Paul
M.

Provide information to someone that's performing the experiments and some of them sounds really, really tough to me. In one this one.

But the proposed yeah, I I understand and agree with.

Yeah, but you can do amendment of your plan. You are allowed to do that.

But you have to say that.

Statistical plan has been changed after knowing about the data then the the results are something if if I I'm reading a paper like that then I would read it with with different eyes I would say.

Yeah, I can understand that.

But what would be the advantage if you?

Pre inform your analysis plan and after that you describe that you changed your analysis because of the way the data look like to me. I mean I can't. I can't see a clear advantage for.

And and I do systematic reviews there for for assessment of a substance. And if I would come across a study like that I would be very cautious to draw any conclusion from the study.

Because it they they are just change it. Then they explain.

Oh.

Absolutely. If you change the analysis plan after knowing about the data after knowing about the data that's important, then I would not draw any firm conclusion out of it.

Absolutely. For risk assessment, I would not do that.

Yeah.

Yeah, I will see if.

I would just look it as an information, but not not really. Base my conclusion on it.

Whaley, Paul
So, Participant, you're just responding.

Yeah, I'll look into the.

That's to to to show why, why, from my point of view, it's so important.

Whaley, Paul

But honestly, we're just gonna Participant's just responding to you, I think.

Yeah, it does raise a flag, but if they have provided rationale for changing the plane, for example, the data distribution was not as they planned, and therefore violating the assumption of their original planned analyse method, I think it's totally logic.

The judgement reason to change the analyse so I would not blankly.

Exclude their impact, I mean decrease their impact but see if there is a reason we definitely want to avoid prevalue hacking, run all kinds of programmes and see which ones suit your original hypothesis better. But I think it's a it's a responsible thing to do when you see the.

The original plan was not.

Be valid and change accordingly.

Yeah, you can change it. I think no problem at all.

You can do that.

Whaley, Paul

I think so. I think we've established then. So for our purposes here, I mean this is a really interesting discussion and I I love the discussion of pre registration. It's just one of my favourite things right now. But I think we should not ever indulge me. I think we've established that this is an important issue. Obviously sometimes these things will be handled well and sometimes there won't be handled very well and our invites in should be able to distinguish or help people distinguish between those.

Whaley, Paul

I think probably we should move on to the next theme so.

Whaley, Paul

We're satisfied that we've actually covered everything here. Through that discussion we just had. So I'm going to move us on to the next domain, which is our second catchall domain.

Whaley, Paul

Which was the ones which were so confusing we couldn't even put them in meta bias. We might get through these quite quickly, so this is just distortion results due to factors other than those described in the set Co Subs or subcoomains.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

The only theme that really kind of came through this was how you handle issues that you had that the appraisal tool hadn't really anticipated, right? So that other domain that you'll have seen in some risky bar assessment tools already.

Whaley, Paul

So in terms of specific items around this, there was the five that we had were other factors, freedom from other issues, other source of bias, other threats, steps to reduce bias.

Whaley, Paul

How do you think that we could constructively or usefully handle these other issues when it comes to?

Whaley, Paul

Thinking about biased concepts.

Whaley, Paul

Do you have any thoughts?

Whaley, Paul

Or is your thoughts something like? Well something like that would probably do it.

Whaley, Paul

Participant, you've made the mistake of smiling there, so I assume that you probably say something.

Whaley, Paul

Hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Yep.

Yeah. I mean, I find it very difficult to distinguish between all of these. You know, they are kind of other you know. So yeah, I don't have much to add and no good suggestions if I'm honest. But yeah, looking at these, I mean, it's incredibly difficult to capture this kind of other nonspecific.

It seems to be a safety net questions. Did we miss any other questions? Anything that raise a red flag? You want to point out?

Whaley, Paul

My answer is always no, I'm tired now.

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Not entirely satisfactory, I suspect.

But is the question as well to include.

This as like other buyers as a an item into the tool.

No.

Whaley, Paul

We don't really know what to do with it, right and there wasn't consensus on what to do. So we had this kind of cluster of other and it was just like a bit of a difficult.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Yeah, because I like I've seen that in other in other tools and I think it's, I mean it's it's good to have an open area like in case you have an article or a study that is raises other flags. But obviously like right now it's difficult to to know since it's not so specific.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

I agree with that. Yeah, we we did it in sometimes that we have also this other factors.

But others, and it did varies from from subject to subject.

Whaley, Paul

So we need an other which is not quite sure how it should look, so we will think about that. So now we'll move on to something more specific again. So this is performance bias. So we had 20 items where we didn't achieve consensus in or out under performance bias. This is a bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure.

Whaley, Paul

So there's, I mean, there's a lot of items and quite a wide variety of themes that came across from the Delphi and from the items themselves. So there's the issue of router administration of exposure. Ah, yes.

When you say.

Received exposure. You know we are talking about the the exposure concentration in the media or are we talking about internal?

Concentration that achieved.

Whaley, Paul

I don't know.

And and and again.

Whaley, Paul

This is one of the challenges of adapting.

Yeah.

Sorry.

Yeah. So I yeah, again, I'm. I'm advocating my earlier idea of separating the exposure, the outside versus the internal dose, the.

And not to code internal dose as exposure.

Whaley, Paul

So. So Participant, we'll just come to you, but I'm just gonna ask you a couple of clarifying questions first, if that's OK.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

So I mean so when you say so, which Participant, which do you think the exposure is in an in vitro study like if you had to?

I would say that's what's outside of the your test system, so be just now. If you use a skins size, that's what you add onto the size, and if you use.

The cells, that's what you add a 2 outside of the cells.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Whaley, Paul

Good. So Participant.

Yeah, just want to to to.

Raise a point regarding this outsider, medium and internal concentration because.

Treatment can affect the self phenotype by binding to the cell surface, so it's not outside.

Or internal or changing the internal concentration so.

It it it's it's really.

Difficult. I mean, I think to to establish this distinguish between.

So the the received concentration or the received exposure is in my opinion clearly the concentration in the medium. This is what can be controlled compared between different experiments.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Whaley, Paul

Are there circumstances?

Whaley, Paul

In which?

Whaley, Paul

Sorry there's, I guess, probably a couple of things here. So I think one of the things that is quite this, this concept of exposure is quite broad between the.

Whaley, Paul

For the the.

There.

Whaley, Paul

Conceptual schema of bias that we're working with, so exposure is is anything that the cells are exposed to. So like the surrounding environment, so the cell culture environment and things would also count as part of the exposure, right. So it's not just the thing that you're.

Whaley, Paul

Deliberately modifying so with what your the chemical you're dosing the cells with it would also be the incubation temperature, because obviously if you if you if you have a slightly low incubation average that can that can affect the results. The study and things like that. But I think that this this challenge over that seems to me to be relatively straightforward to understand. The challenge is what counts when you're administering the chemical as to what's the received.

Whaley, Paul

Exposure is because these these concept was just also to clarify was very much.

Whaley, Paul

Developed in the context of like you know you you give somebody a pill, so maybe a vitamin D supplement or something and the vitamin D supplement isn't very digestible. So you give them a like 100 microgram supplement, but maybe only 10 micrograms is actually absorbed. Also the true doses

10 micrograms. So what does that 100 micrograms, 10 micrograms, yes, the trulos 10 micrograms even though the administered dose is 100. So the received exposure would in fact probably be 10.

Whaley, Paul

But I will let you do all the talking at this point, so your first.

Now we we have that situation and then we talk about the external exposure and internal exposure also in the animal experiments because that is a difference from the external to the internal exposure. And here I I would say we have to measure both. We have to measure the concentration in the medium and the concentration in the cell. And I can tell you I have some example with modelling where I can show you that it is very important to have the measurement in the cell.

Whaley, Paul

M.

Whaley, Paul

Is that can you share an example either now or after the call, just so we can?

I can. I can. I can send you the publications. Yeah.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

That'll be very helpful. Thank you. Participant, you're next.

I I'm I agree very much because I mean because of different factors in, in the surroundings or the material being used there. Like if there's no measurement of the chemicals in the medium or even in the cell.

Then I would assume there's a big unknown, a big uncertainty around these data so.

Absolutely, yeah.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I would think it's very important.

Whaley, Paul

K then we go up country on the next.

Yeah, I'm not. I just want to point out that I'm not arguing that it's not important to measure.

In turn, the intracellular concentration of a chemical understood, but I'm trying to say is that there is difference.

Potentially very significant difference between intracellular concentration and.

A binding event or for example a low affinity binding event that doesn't change the intercellular concentration and it's too it's very important. So if you want to.

Consider all the important situation we would have to measure outside medium concentration, intracellular concentration and binding to cell to the cell surface for example.

Yeah, absolutely, yeah.

It's it's even more complicated. This is what I'm trying to point out.

Yeah, yeah, yeah. Cool.

But depending on your outcome as well, right on your chosen outcome.

Yeah. I always, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

OK. So Participant, you're next.

I want to talk about the terms that people generally use. Umm, the conditions of the experiment versus exposure in visual studies. Typically the difference between your treatment groups and control group is the only the exposure part or the other conditions should be maintained the same and so they. Therefore traditionally they are not counted as exposure, even though in in other studies they may be considered may be considered.

Part of the exposure.

Yeah. Yes.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So I think one of the things that came across from so, actually I think we might just be touching on the differential and non differential bias issue here, so.

Whaley, Paul

If there are differences between groups in the exploration conditions, obviously that's going to introduce like.

Whaley, Paul

A.

Whaley, Paul

Bias one or the other, but you can also have non differential bias where if you just systematically like under incubated like you you all of your incubators are a temperature that's too low compared to everybody else's studies, you're going to potentially have.

Whaley, Paul

You're going to be biased away from what everybody else is finding who's been using the incubators at the correct temperatures, right? So.

Whaley, Paul

I think one of the issues that maybe we can just resolve this issue, just immediately before we then move on. So do we agree?

Whaley, Paul

Even nondifferential bias should be taken into account when assessing the potential for bias in a study, right?

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I think it's important to consider, but we need to make it clear in the questionnaire what we're talking about because that's.

Deviate from the typical.

Normal creatures.

Whaley, Paul

OK, fantastic. So, go ahead.

No, no, it's not me.

Whaley, Paul

It wasn't you. OK, so I grew just to capture that we've got.

Whaley, Paul

Some potential, maybe some assumptions or automatic ways of reading invites in that come from specific ways of talking about these issues in an in vitro context that we need to make sure we're very, very clear about and differentiating the what I'm calling the moment the non differential issues around exposure versus the differential issues.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good. So you have that please, whatever comment you're going to make in a minute ago is all yours?

Right now, I was coming back, but maybe that was all to clarify, maybe that is the different exposure. So we have what we talked about too. We said we have the nominal exposure, this is the contain containion you you add to the cell medium or or to the cells and that is usually what is considered exposure level. But then of course you have to consider.

The actual concentration is there medium because some of the chemical might might bind to the plastics or whatever and then we have the internal concentration in the cells. But as you add mentioned of course not, it's not always some chemicals don't act, they act on on membrane receptors for example. Then the internal concentration maybe not so relevant, especially the concentration in the medium that reaches to the receptor. So but these different three types of different concentrations.

Are usually can you can be consider and and they are.

It's important to think that the nominal concentration that you you think you are you are exposing yourselves to is maybe not the concentration that they are actually exposed to because.

Whaley, Paul

Right. So I think we'll move on to specific items.

Whaley, Paul

Route of administration of exposure. Does it make any sense to talk about route of administration when it comes to in vitro studies?

Whaley, Paul

Fairly firm. Shake your heads if you could just verbalise for the transcript. Why? And then we can capture that and we can, Participant.

To me, doesn't make sense.

Whaley, Paul

Okie Dokie and that's do you have anything to add?

Whaley, Paul

Nope. OK.

No, actually to me it doesn't make any sense either because there's not so many.

Variations of the.

Route of exposure.

Whaley, Paul

Good. Thank you. OK, so.

Whaley, Paul

About this item independent characterization of oh, you had a right.

Right. It's sorry, Paul. Yeah. Yeah. Sorry, Paul. Yeah. Say, I agree with destivity. In most cases, it does not make sense, but in some type of of of sale assays, you might actually not you might expose through through air in this type of air liquid celestic exposure actually air in the Chamber and not actually add to the chemical into the medium. So that could be different route so exposure but it's not exactly as we mean for newer studies.

So I would also agree this is probably not so important. It can be too bit confusing to include this one.

But you certain?

Perhaps that can be one of the specific type of exposure that we were discussing, because Air Liquid interface, once you could have.

A cells being submerged deep.

You can have a thin layer of media on top of cell. You can have the media syncs below the cell levels and so I think that that.

Seems to be 3 different routes of.

Exposure and the very distinctive from each other. So I would suggest this put into the.

Subcategories now along with the soluble chemicals particles versus vapour.

Whaley, Paul

OK, so we've got.

Yeah, I agree.

Whaley, Paul

3rd module potentially then so that is what were they called again, Participant?

For chemical part, there is the the soluble chemical, the particle and vapour.

Whaley, Paul

Later. Thank you.

And for the the air liquid interface, then that's the test system.

Whaley, Paul
So.

Whaley, Paul
So just thinking about this screw, we might want to consider. So for Robin Z, what they do is they have a have like a pre application step for a tool where they identify the type of study they're working with and where the potential confounders can come from for that type of study. It might be important if we're dealing with multiple study designs that I mean it might we have to consider whether or not a modular approach to dealing with this.

Whaley, Paul
Is appropriate? Or maybe there's a way of dealing with this where we have a set of establishing questions if you like that set up the evaluation process and properly takes into account the type of study in vitro study design that's being dealt with, right?

Whaley, Paul
That might be quite complicated, but it might solve as a problem I don't know.

Whaley, Paul
Just a thought.

Yeah, just commenting on yes, just comment in in, in also one possibility as we've done in the in the syrup tool, which is kind of similar to where we have in that case you can decide in advance which criteria are not applicable for this type of study design for example or this type of analysis you're doing and then you can remove those. So that could be included, but some in this case if I would have this router administration exposure then that one would remove.

That criteria, if it would be a normal cell culture study, because then it's not relevant, but maybe for some air liquid culture this might be relevant.

Whaley, Paul
Yes, that would be another potential approach we could take as well. So that would be analogous to the also analogous to the ohat tool.

Whaley, Paul
For.

Whaley, Paul
Human and animal studies, where depending on study design you use different questions from the tool.

Whaley, Paul
That'll be a tree structure, I think.

Whaley, Paul
OK, good. So moving on to independent characterization of exposure, this is something that came up a lot in the included.

Whaley, Paul
Written tools that we were looking at, possibly because quite a lot of them were drawn from the same sources.

Whaley, Paul

And you're thinking how what does independent characterization of exposure mean and when do you think it might be important and when not as we're trying to understand lack of consensus?

If I can start, I think this is what we discussed just a minute ago. So these are these are exactly in this independent collection exposure could be actually measurement of the exposure levels in the culture medium or possibly in the cells. So this is like you have the nominal exposure, this is what you think you're adding and then you can characterise the exposure by this different types of measurement independent. This may be a bit strange idea, but characterization exposure this could be in that case this could be relevant.

Whaley, Paul

Is it possible that independent characterization exposure in this case means having a third party audit?

No.

Whaley, Paul

Your.

Whaley, Paul

OK, good. That's good.

So I think when I think about independent characterization, I think about chemical purity testing and not so much about the exposure, it's how it's done.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

So if we're talking about chemical purity testing.

Whaley, Paul

Does that change people's perception of how important this item might be?

Whaley, Paul

Ur.

It remains important.

I mean, we have for the for the personal a we have created exclusion criteria if security was less than 95% when we did the FSR.

Systematic.

Assessment.

So, but it is not characterization of exposure that is just the purity of the material.

Mm.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

Yeah. And I think independent measurement of exposure would be better.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul
OK. We'll take that into account. So the next item, 373 is interesting because it has a couple of terms in there. Obviously that were confusing. So if ignoring well, let's change care of the investigator.

Whaley, Paul
And participant for sample.

Whaley, Paul
Would that make more sense as a statement in relation to in vitro studies?

Obviously.

Whaley, Paul
Yes.

Ha ha ha ha.

Whaley, Paul
So I think we've probably dealt with that one.

Whaley, Paul
In terms of.

Whaley, Paul
Things like so 1099 order of reading of samples. This is something that I, if I recall correctly it came up as being thought potentially quite important in the focus groups because there was concerned that if you read the samples or potentially you know you could also pass out in the same order right by the time you've got to the end of your 96 well plate or whatever or your row of patchy dishes on your desk. The Patri dish on the end.

Whaley, Paul
Could end up being in quite different environmental circumstances if you like.

Whaley, Paul
The first one right so.

Whaley, Paul
I mean, I guess it might be difficult practically to address this issue, but do you think it is of high theoretical importance?

Yes.

Definitely.

Whaley, Paul
Yes, definitely.

I think that that at least I know that that you.

Look at the time you give in to material and you you do the reading and that is absolutely important because the exposure time would be different.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

So it's not a theoretical problem, it's it's. It's a real problem I think.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm. OK, so that sounds like it.

In particular, if you look after after immediate responses.

30.

Whaley, Paul
Then.

Whaley, Paul
Look, I had to learn it, please.

Yeah, I'm not sure if it's sorry, Paul. Yeah, it's just adding that. Yeah.

Maybe order is not that. Yeah. Obviously it's important in in an experiment like also I mentioned all of that I quick and fast response, but yeah maybe this 110991 placement of samples has to do with in terms of randomization of.

Of plague design.

And randomization of reading, you know, if you guarantee both of this, maybe the order is not that the order of readings is not that important.

So does that this item maybe fit better for the detection bias or?

Whaley, Paul
Potentially, I think we might have put it here because we were thinking that it's something that the investigator is doing that changes that kind of. But you're right, they could well fit under detection bias. We're not. There are some items that we just weren't sure and just put somewhere as our best guess and our best guess evolves over time.

Yeah. Then it would be order of exposing the samples.

For the performance.

Whaley, Paul
Probably. I mean that was we had the item that we were dealing with, so yeah.

Whaley, Paul
In terms of I'm sure.

Whaley, Paul
I get a bit of a headache when I think about stuff sometimes. So in terms of.

Whaley, Paul
So the reason I think machine for petting ended up in the list of items was that by handing over some of these processes to robots right, you can have more control over the environmental conditions in which an explosion is ministered, because you can put the robot in the incubator, for example. I guess

the passing could be more accurate, you can have, you know, can code where the exposure is applied, which allows for better control of which.

Whaley, Paul

Maybe randomization things? Is it the sort of thing that if you saw in a study?

Whaley, Paul

You might feel better about the study, or is it something that is just a method that is used that is used well or used badly and doesn't make any difference to your sense of potential for bias?

Whaley, Paul

I.

Whaley, Paul

M.

I tend to think it's probably more consistent, but I also have heard horror stories about machine pipetting carry the contaminations throughout the whole plate. It's not a guarantee, but I think it's a it's a tool that that could make it more consistent.

Point, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I think one of the problems is that if they if machine perpetuating is used, it probably also correlates to studies that are able to do more repeats or something like that. So it well it's not a problem, but it probably isn't indicated. It is maybe a more robust study than what you could do with one person hand to petting.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

We can have more power or reproducibility. Yep.

Potentially, but yeah. Obviously it's a positive pros and cons.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Whaley, Paul

Then there was this item which will be the last one we do today. I think so. This item of crosstalk between signalling pathways where there was definitely some confusion as to why that was in there.

Whaley, Paul

Can somebody help us figure out what that meant? Sorry, was trying to get lost. It might.

Whaley, Paul

Would crosstalk be a potential bias issue or not basically.

Whaley, Paul

Participant, you look like you want to say something, so I'm gonna pee on the spot.

Yeah, that for me, this is the reality. This is the biology, the different signalling pathways have common players have compensation. Have umm feedback loops. So the cross talk is it's not a bias. It's just what the biological system.

Whaley, Paul
M.

Would do and so I'm I think perhaps the question was on interpreting your results.

You need to consider the influence from other signalling pathways that you are focusing on.

But by itself, I don't think it's a performance bias.

Whaley, Paul
OK, very good.

Yeah, I agree. Yeah.

I agree with you.

Whaley, Paul
Excellent. So I.

Me too.

Yeah, me too.

Whaley, Paul
Eliminate that fantastic good of our rare eliminations. So I think that we can stop so we can stop exactly at the bottom of the hour. Thank you very, very much for your energetic and enthusiastic contribution to this has been hugely helpful, even if it is still a bit confusing. So bear with us while we work all this out. We'll have one more group. We should get everything finished by the end of this week. Then we'll analyse the feedback from the discussions and then we should be in a pretty good position to.

Whaley, Paul
Uh present the final results of the Delphi process in a manuscript. Now we're thinking like we were thinking we would put the Delphi manuscript in with the with the Delphi method in with the final tool manuscripts. But we're thinking now, given the amounts of information data processing that we're doing, that will probably keep all separate now. So it'll be an additional paper.

Workshop 16.05.2024

Whaley, Paul
So just to refresh you one where at and what we're doing here? So we're developing invites in. So I'm hope you're aware by now a tool for assessing the internal validity of an in vitro study by which means potential for systematic error in results or findings of the study. The intent is for this tool to be used in systematic reviews in support of chemical assessment. What we did was we collected potential bias criteria from existing study assessment tools to a literature review.

Whaley, Paul

And then we ran some focus groups to collect additional criteria from expert opinion that weren't necessarily represented in the tools that were in our literature review. And what we're doing now through this Delphi or modified Delphi method, is prioritising items for inclusion in the draught invites in tool. Yes, using this modified Delphi approach.

Whaley, Paul

What we found in the Delphi was that some items did not achieve consensus as either for being appropriate for consideration when evaluating the internal bids and vitro study.

Whaley, Paul

Nor were they was that consensus on there being inappropriate, so they kind of stayed in the pool of criterion concepts that we're trying to evaluate for relevance through in vitro study risk of assessment. So the purpose of these post early discussions is to inform our decisions as a research team on how to handle these items of unclear.

Whaley, Paul

Relevance. So what we'll do today is clear. Discuss and clarify with you what the items might mean in relation to in vitro studies.

Whaley, Paul

And get your opinion as their importance when it comes to the potential for introducing systematic error into an in vitro study.

Whaley, Paul

We're not at this stage discussing whether an item should be in a final tool. We're just trying to get a handle on whether the concept that is expressed by the item might be important for introducing bias.

Whaley, Paul

So yes, this is very much to help us inform our final decisions essentially because obviously we've got too many items to go through one by one in the fire, you know, sensible amount of time.

Whaley, Paul

So we're gonna use today's discussions of specific items and themes to make decisions about which items get put forward for use in the tool and which ones we can kind of safely exclude.

Whaley, Paul

What I'm going to do is show you the domain that the item is under the definition of the domain, and then the number of items where we didn't achieve consensus within that domain.

Whaley, Paul

We'll have structured discussion of the items which are grouped according to common issues in relation to comments from the Delphi.

Whaley, Paul

And the it's kind of thematic focus of the items. So sort of some combination of those and we're going to prioritise identifying what items had poor consensus because they were unclear and get a sense of direction, of consensus when the issues relating to those items have been clarified.

Whaley, Paul

Yep, each discussion group has been discussing different domains.

Whaley, Paul

And the domains are there to help structure discussion. So we're not really discussing here whether the domains are inappropriate or complete classification scheme for biases. They're just an organising principle to help us chunk up discussions and make the process of discussing these things kind of tractable.

Whaley, Paul

So I've got these 12 domains, so analysis bias, attrition bias, choice of question bias, conflicted interest bias. Compounding can vary bias detection bias, meta bias, other performance bias, reporting bias, selection bias and time of study determination bias.

Whaley, Paul

The first group work their way through to detection bias.

Whaley, Paul

The second group kind of finished off the unfinished work of Group One on detection bias and went through method bias. Other and performance bias.

Whaley, Paul

Is kind of big, so it was a likely discussion.

Whaley, Paul

And then today, we're hoping to get through reporting bias, selection bias and timing of study termination bias with you.

Whaley, Paul

So for administrative information, this session is being recorded and machine transcribed.

Whaley, Paul

The data from the machine transcription will be anonymised.

Whaley, Paul

We'd ask you to not at a later date attribute any comments to specific individuals for running these workshops under Chatham House rules and anonymity. Participation is obviously very important. I am your facilitator being supported by Goon who's helping keep me on time. Steer me along Guru is our note takers today.

Whaley, Paul

I agree is also the project supervisor and lead, so if you have any questions or concerns about the process, if you could raise them now or you can follow up after us with grew with any other remaining concerns. So is everything satisfactory and to your comfort.

Whaley, Paul

Start affirmative. Yes, from everybody. Very good.

Whaley, Paul

So just a quick recording. Check. Goon. Are we picking everyone up? OK, on the transcription.

Gunn Elisabeth Vist

We are indeed yes, thank you.

Whaley, Paul

Very good.

Whaley, Paul

OK, my submission. This isn't it. OK, so I'm going to start with reporting bias. So we have three items, of which the doubtfully process didn't resolve the relevance of evaluation of internal witnesses in vitro studies.

Whaley, Paul

So reporting bias we defined as a bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings. OK.

Whaley, Paul

Is that definition reasonably clear to you? Do you have any questions or comments?

Whaley, Paul

Not a very serious spaces.

Whaley, Paul

I get some shaking of heads, so I assume that means that you don't have any questions rather than the definitions unclear. So we have kind of two themes amongst these three items.

Whaley, Paul

So was the handling of post hoc analysis in reporting research and then selective presentation of data and results.

Whaley, Paul

It's only got 3 items, so it can look all three of them. So we have this issue of item 115 approach to reporting results 109 approach. The presentation of data on 180 selective emphasis on post hoc analysis. So as it relates to potential for introducing bias when you are reporting the results or findings of the study, do any of these seem to be particularly irrelevant or relevant or do you have any thoughts as to?

Whaley, Paul

Why it might be that we didn't achieve consensus on these items.

Whaley, Paul

But one of your spots in a second?

Whaley, Paul

Well, so we can't hear heads shaking. So I'm gonna say so. Participant, you're shaking your head there. Would you like to just comment briefly as to how your reaction to this?

Whaley, Paul

You only saw me, so yeah.

You know, I mean, it looked like they they all look pretty straightforward to me.

So I don't know why I don't. Maybe we'll get into the details why 'cause, there's some consensus wasn't reached, but.

That's OK.

Right.

Whaley, Paul

We don't know why consensus wasn't reached. This is why we're having these workshops. So we're asking you. So yeah, .

Yeah. It's so I think my own vote for these was that they were well for some of these, like for statistics.

I was kind of going off the IRS approach, which is what we use.

Because we don't put that much emphasis on on stats. Since we can theoretically redo them ourselves if we really want to use this data.

So we so we tend to deemphasize that in our study evaluations.

So when I was filling out the survey, I.

Take that same approach.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

That it was less important. So maybe our is that what this is referring to like a?

Whaley, Paul

So I think the.

Working analysis of data.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So it's really about select, it's, I mean the whole, the whole domain, right, is about being selective in what what data is reported, what results are reported. So you know the classic situation and clinical trials and healthcare research would be.

Whaley, Paul

Something like outcome switching would be an example of reporting bias. So you go into the study saying you're going to find one thing, you've got a null result there, but your secondary outcome had a positive result. So you promote the secondary outcome and you just don't mention the fact that the primary outcome had a null result.

OK.

Whaley, Paul

And that might completely disappear from the study report. So there'll be very little opportunity for anybody to.

Whaley, Paul

Figure out what the true results of the study was, even by maybe real analysing the data or something sometimes so.

Whaley, Paul

Well, that's fine.

OK, I see. So my comment about stats wasn't really that relevant. Yeah, I'm not sure. I'm not sure why this.

Would have a lack of consensus.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. OK, Participant.

You good? OK. So I was thinking about this in the in the context of.

Sometimes the so a few things, there's actually a pretty wide variety of in vitro studies that I am familiar with and in some cases it does make sense to be more selective in what you report, especially in detail. And so it's a matter of not necessarily leaving things out.

Of the reporting, but which ones you actually emphasise versus put in the supplemental is somewhat guided by the type of assay and the type of publication you're putting it in. So I think some of that.

My concern about dinging things for being.

Not of quality or having a high BIOS because of the approach to reporting has so many other factors involved that it seems.

Challenging to that's that's I think why there's potentially not consensus here.

Whaley, Paul

OK, so but could it be an important? Could it be something that'd be worth potentially taking into consideration if we're trying to understand whether or not we're being misled by a given in vitro study manuscript, right.

Whaley, Paul

Could it be the case? Yeah.

Yes, I guess maybe I was thinking to the next step is how do you do that consistently when there's external factors that influence that?

Right.

Whaley, Paul

That's true. I think we're trying to view that as a separate problem. So I think this is something that's come across from the these discussions is that we probably perhaps not clear enough.

Whaley, Paul

When we're setting up the Delfi that we think there's a difference between the importance of.

Whaley, Paul

The potential factors it relates to introducing bias and the practicality of eliminating that factor, right. So other other discussion groups like you know, it's very hard to blind surgical interventions because it's really difficult.

Whaley, Paul

For to for a surgeon to like, you know, cutting someone, cutting off someone's leg, you pretty much know you're doing it, and if you're blind to surgeon whilst they're trying to cut off someone's leg, then it can be really bad for patient outcomes. So typically you wouldn't blind surgical interventions. It can be very hard to do that, but it doesn't mean that lack of blinding isn't important, even when it's very difficult to eliminate. So it could be practically difficult to deal with. But still, theoretically it will still be real importance. And then there's the other thing, which is the how does one go about?

Whaley, Paul

Establishing whether or not this biasing factor is present is also a separate issue, because it can be very hard to detect the bias. But still the bias could be very important, right?

Yeah. So I guess I would, I would feel that these, especially the first two, I haven't thought about the third one yet today. The first two could definitely introduce internal bias.

However, I think they would be really challenging to evaluate consistently across even just in vitro assays.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I mean, selective reporting is a nightmare to deal with because you've very, very rarely got any evidence for it because the whole point of it is that, you know, a researcher would be.

Whaley, Paul

Holding back.

Whaley, Paul

The information they found was less helpful to whatever case they might be trying to make and pushing forward the information it is and we know that reporting advice is, you know, in some areas of research quite rampant. But.

Whaley, Paul

And and difficult to diagnose and difficult to prevent.

Whaley, Paul

But still important.

Whaley, Paul

Umm, so this item 180, so this selective emphasis on post hoc analysis. This is the idea that I think that in in some research, in some studies you'll have a clear plan for what the study intends to.

Whaley, Paul

Investigate or analyse or determine right.

Whaley, Paul

And that will be done according to some kind of pre specified plan in some way.

Whaley, Paul

Amount of pre specification of important probably this point, but then they'll also do some secondary analysis and things.

Whaley, Paul

Which are unplanned and maybe exploratory in nature rather than kind of hypothesis testing in nature so they can and then some of that exploratory analysis can be due to the way it's presented in a study can be.

Whaley, Paul

Presented as if it was hypothesis testing, right. So if you do like, you know 100 tests on the data, 100 analysis on the data.

Whaley, Paul

And they get 3 or 4 positive findings. Sometimes some studies will promote those three or four findings as if they were pre specified at some way. Hypotheses test it, but actually there could just be like a statistical artefact result of multiple testing. Right? So.

Whaley, Paul

Some tools risk advice, tools, prompts people to look for this issue.

Whaley, Paul

And would view those small number of positive results out of an undeclared, you know, hundred tests as being.

Whaley, Paul

Undermining certainty or increasing potential bias in those small positives, positive results. Does that sound like a sensible thing to look for? Team? Did that make any sense?

Whaley, Paul

We got some nods about bring on set all those OK, so I think.

Yeah. And given given the number of potential tests in many in vitro testing scenarios, that could really be a huge a huge issue. 'cause you can find lots of false positives then.

Whaley, Paul

It OK, so I guess I think we have enough information then to make our decisions on these items. So we will move on to the next set 'cause. There's quite a lot to deal with it.

Whaley, Paul

So this is a selection bias. It's probably the last like big domain where there are lots and lots of items where there was.

Whaley, Paul

Some was lack of consensus, so here we've define selection bias as a bias resulting from one or three off methods used to select subjects or data in a study.

Whaley, Paul

Factors that influence initial study participation, so that's entry into a study or differences between the study sample and the population of interest.

Whaley, Paul

So I think some of the issues here in relation to the definition and also to the uh items are about confusion about what population means in this context.

Whaley, Paul

What participation means in the in vitro concepts and what things like selection of subjects means in the in vitro context? Does that speak to you for at all as to maybe an explanation as to why we struggle to get consensus on so many of these items?

Whaley, Paul

Yes.

Yes, yes, I think that's exactly where I was struggling and seeing some of the comments from other folks on the survey, it seemed like.

We weren't all on the same page with what these different terms meant in the context of mid vitro.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

I think that's fair enough, yeah.

Whaley, Paul

OK, so the themes that came through.

Whaley, Paul

For the selection bias issues, was the relevance of randomization of samples.

Whaley, Paul

And and vitro studies, where some people saying that all samples are identical, so randomization doesn't matter.

Whaley, Paul

The inclusion of samples due to specific characteristics of these samples.

Whaley, Paul

Came up.

Whaley, Paul

Other randomization procedures.

Whaley, Paul

You know, my hair measurement feels actually I checked my notes there so as other randomization procedures and their appropriateness in in vitro contacts.

Whaley, Paul

The representativeness of the sample, says selection of included samples, I think, is probably fairly similar to previous bullets. The retention rejection samples at point of entry in the study and then the difference in participant and sample. So these are kind of six quite complicated issues. So it might be worth just running through them all at a time so.

Whaley, Paul

I'm trying to think of why randomization of samples has ended up under selection bias good. Can you just help me out here and promptly? Thank you. So the end of a long week. So my brain is also not working properly.

No, I don't have an explanation ready for you.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Whaley, Paul

Yes, maybe that'll come clear as we move further on. So something that may definitely be an issue, something's definitely an issue in the.

Whaley, Paul

Tools for develop for assessing risk of bias in control trials. So RCT is either animal studies or or people.

Whaley, Paul

Is that?

Whaley, Paul

Sometimes the way in which people are selected for inclusion of study, I think this is where the randomization comes in means that there are associations between the features, those say those people have and why they end up in the study right with one arm of the study or another. So like a classic issue with.

Whaley, Paul

Animal studies is that if you take the first, you've got 12 rats in a cage and you pick out the rats first. Six rats go in the first.

Whaley, Paul

The exposure arm of the study, the second six rats go in the control arm of the study and imagine if you're testing for behavioural changes in the rest or something, you always the first six rats you pick out will be the bravest, boldest, most curious rats. And the rats you pick out second will be the ones hiding in the corner of the most timid. So the systematic behavioural difference between those rats, that's determined how they end up in the control or exposure on the study. And then that distorts the finding of the study.

Whaley, Paul

So you prevent this issue with randomization by randomly selecting the rats. So the baseline characteristics, if you like of the control arm and the exposure arm are the same. That's why randomization comes in. I remember now.

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

Do you think this comes into play in in vitro studies? Do you think it doesn't? Do you think it depends? I'm just kind of interested as to what you think about this, how you respond.

Yeah, I know that for some of the experiment you have a random in randomization of the other different. Well, in the 19 in white plate. And so you have randomization of the treatment. So it can exist within vitro methods to have a randomization of the of the sample of the A/C.

Not maybe more. More importantly for Pcb's.

Could be also a result from.

As you know, because if you put in a multi wire plate, every positive and negative control always at the same place.

And you have, I don't know why, but for the first row you have.

Systemic difference and in this case you will use ABS for all the study. So maybe I have some randomization could be a good a good thing also.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, so it here, I think. Oh, sorry, Participant.

Yeah, I'm. I'm in agreement with Participant. But this is where this is one got tricky because it's less about the importance of randomising the sample selection and more about randomising the treatments that those samples are exposed to. Because in theory, all your samples should be identical, whether that be because you homogenated whatever your your samples are and and then and then divided them up on the plate.

So that's one area I don't do cell based in vitro assays, but I can imagine there could also be a relevance for randomization of samples if you're doing cell based, if you're selecting the cells from multiple different growth plates so.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

I think randomization is really important and some but it the confusion comes in the randomization of of samples versus treatments, I think is where I got stuck on this.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So we were trying, I mean it's not obvious, but that there's an important difference, right? So there's the randomization of the samples at point of entry into the study. So you've randomly allocated them to treatment groups, right? So it may be a control group days, one days, two days three. And then there's a performance issue where throughout the study there you end up with different exposure profiles because of how the studies performed, which is trying to hold those two ideas separate, I think, or at least some of these.

Whaley, Paul

Bias tools do try to hold those two ideas separate.

Whaley, Paul

So if you've got made this idea of homogeneity, we can just return to it, because like obviously in some in vitro study designs, you're going to have follow genius cultures. And that's means that randomization is less likely to be important. But if you could have baseline differences between samples, particularly in like very sensitive assays or something I could foresee, if you're not randomising how the samples get allocated to.

Whaley, Paul

Exposure or treatment.

Whaley, Paul

Groups, right?

Whaley, Paul

Then you could have systematic differences in the cells between those different in the samples between those groups, and then you would have a problem with the results of your assay. Would that be reasonable?

Well, even even on a 96 well plate, you could have.

Different performance of the samples on there, but the at least most of the methods I'm familiar with, you load your samples 1st and then you randomise the treatments onto them.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. Yep.

And so that's where in practicality you are randomising the samples that are there, but it's actually in practise you're randomising the treatments.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So you still have random allocation of.

Whaley, Paul

Sample.

To treatment group.

Whaley, Paul

To I'm going to call it study on June Group. Yep. OK.

Whaley, Paul

Participant, sorry Participant. First, sorry.

Not sure to be sure to be first so, but I totally agree.

That the most important maybe is to have three independent experiment at the end. So you have randomization at at the end because you make 3 and geological.

3D Yeah, 3 biological replicate. So at the end you could have three the independent treatment and also you can change where you put the cell treaty then cell not treated and your positive control and negative control. So you have some.

I'm the musician at the end and you have two replicates, so in my mind it's a it's a good thing to do, to be sure to not have abs.

Specific of the of the method of the treatment or whatever.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good, Participant.

So I I agree with the randomization of treatment. My only thought was I was wondering how common that really is.

I feel like every in vitro. Granted, I I was, you know, in grad school when I was doing in vitro essays. But every essay I ever did involve doing a serial dilution. So it was not random at all. It was, you know, everything in a row.

So. So while it does seem important in terms of the placement on the plates.

You know, I I feel like it's it's not.

Not done very often.

Whaley, Paul

That's possibly so.

Whaley, Paul

One of the so this is something else that's come up in the other groups, right, is that it's not common, right. So we end up dinging all studies for being biassed in the same way. And what I think we're also trying to separate out the importance of the issue from its kind of commonness, right. So, you know, back in the 1970s, before it was standard, literary views to assess risk and bias, people were less aware of what study practises.

Whaley, Paul

Introduced bias and what?

Whaley, Paul

Well, sort of protected against it. So like effective randomization was much less common in the 1970s than it became by the 1990s because it took systematic reviews and risky bar assessment to discover that these desirable practises were much less prevalent than would be hoped. And it resulted in

spread of these desirable practises and research methods and proved to the result. So in the short term, it's probably going to, it might make things look a bit iffy. But in the long term could be beneficial to the research field. So we don't want to be in a position where we're not assessing something because it.

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Is awkward rather than because it's important, right?

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

That's true. Yeah, it is acknowledging the source of bias. OK, yeah, that's good point.

And.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, do not have to punish people or Ding people. I think like this, that's supposed to be an objective assessment of study limitations and then we have to make the best use of that as we can. So are you saying that?

Yeah, I had a similar comment to Participant, because I think all of these are very important, but.

In terms of like, I mean most of this information, if you could take just a study from the peer review and try to evaluate all of these components, you're probably not going to have sufficient information to sort of say either way, do they randomise, do they not that they look at this. So most of the time with the intent to be to how would you grade that cause most of the time you're not going to have that type of information. And I know this is also.

Serves as an educational tool, so for investigators, for people that are doing research, these are the.

You know things that we look at and we're evaluating.

A study an in vitro study but but yeah, in terms of the actual evaluation, what would be did you just report it as?

As a known or.

Would you actually downgrade the study? I guess? How would you handle this when you don't have this level of detail?

Whaley, Paul

So we don't know the answer to that yet because at this stage we're just trying to identify the concepts that need to be analysed and then the type of information and it's how readily available it is and how to respond when the information that would be needed to make a judgement hasn't been provided. We're going to figure out in the course of developing the tool itself. So this is just helps us understand what questions the tool should ask and then how those questions should be asked and how they can be answered and how to rate.

Whaley, Paul

Risk of bias is gonna be a completely separate issue for us at this point.

Whaley, Paul

I think we're gonna expect it to be very common that we don't have the information that we need, right?

Whaley, Paul

I know from our colleagues who do the systematic review of animal studies that they just quite often being like, well, we've got no idea what happened in this study, like for several domains and then trying to understand, to come to a reasonable judgement of risk of bias, I think it's still a, you know, still a contested space. So we're not.

Whaley, Paul

I already want to make any assumptions about how we're going to do that right now.

Whaley, Paul

I think for the notes groove we could just capture. So when I was talking about serial dilutions.

Whaley, Paul

I think when it comes to prompts and things like phrasing like that might be quite important to look for when we're trying to establish whether or not.

Whaley, Paul

Randomization's occurred right. So if we see a phrase like serial dilution, we might be less confident the randomization has occurred for example. So I think we might want to do some research when it comes to the tool development stage into these kinds of trigger phrasing's, we can look for.

Whaley, Paul

Across all the domains, Participant.

Yeah. Just following up on that comment by Participant 'cause. I think she's right that that still is a common practise. So I think one of the challenges might be.

'Cause it's so in the in the work I'm most familiar with, we have some component that's kind of a screening level that has randomization, but then when we dig into the details of a potential positive chemicals, then we end up not having randomization 'cause. We're just doing everything in serial dilution and very organised.

And so, you know, when you have that type of multiple layers or multiple tiers within reported results, that could be challenging to evaluate the randomization. And in one scenario, you think randomization is really important to identify the potential chemicals or treatments of concern. But in the second case, where you're doing those serial dilutions, randomization maybe becomes less important.

Because you need to have that level of structure in the assay.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Yep, that makes sense.

Whaley, Paul

OK so.

Whaley, Paul

This question, this theme of representativeness of sample, I think maybe the next thing to discuss, I think we've probably touched on it already, but.

Whaley, Paul

Maybe it's not. Maybe that's more of an Excel, but just you think, well, let's move on from that. Don't actually discuss that at this stage. When it comes to.

Whaley, Paul

The entry of samples into the study.

Whaley, Paul

When I guess when samples are being like, is there any sense in which you're selecting meaningful sense, which you're selecting samples for inclusion that is analogous to if you've got a rat study and you're literally assigning, you know, rats to the different exposure groups in an animal SA, is there anything analogous in?

Whaley, Paul

In vitro studies where you might be like, imagine you've got 10 rats in an animal SA and you're like, OK, we're going to put eight rats.

Whaley, Paul

To our study, so I'll take this route and I'll I'll have this route. I don't like looking at that route. I'll have that route, that route, that route, that route, not that route. And I'll take that route. So you've got like they've got an issue of selection of some of the rats into the study because you like look of them. And again that kind of could introduce issues into the population in your study or something, sorry, not necessarily even not better being represented the the.

Whaley, Paul

The group that you think you're sampling from.

Whaley, Paul

Participant.

In my mind, you have always within vitro is a positive and negative control in USA. So in the case of your positive control is fine. Normally you have to include every every sample in the in the in the plate or in the assay or wherever if you have. If you can be sure that for this assay is your compound as there are problem for.

Is not mixed well or there are problem of solubility or something like that. Maybe you can ask to see if you include or not this result.

In my.

In my lab, when we perform experiment, if experiment is fine with positive and negative control OK. In this case we include all the point and we did not exclude any treatment.

Whaley, Paul

OK, Participant.

I thought was from my experience with in vitro assays, usually culture yourselves in a bigger container and then you would, you know, take them out and distribute them to your plate for the assay. So taking from the same container the same cell passage number would be important.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm, you see that?

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

The same whatever colony of cells.

Whaley, Paul

You see.

Yeah, I just was gonna add, I mean, you also would have the scenario where you would be isolating cells from an animal, right?

So your example would be in terms of kind of picking the rats.

Umm.

I don't know if that makes sense but.

Whaley, Paul

That doesn't make sense. You know that we have this discussion of primary biological samples and the issues that can be introduced from there. So, OK, so this this is a potentially relevant to the primary biological samples. What if?

Whaley, Paul

Are there so just to follow up on this idea? So the circumstances which maybe you've got some samples, if it's like, I don't know if it's like just like a place or something and you you're trying to, you know, setting up the study and you have a set of place in front of you like well.

Whaley, Paul

So this one looks fine. I don't like the look of this one. This one looks fine. This one looks fine. I don't like the look of this one. Is there a possibility where you know there's there's kind of in a sense eligibility criteria for the inclusion of a plate in the study that you are could be applying could be a subjective judgement and that subjective judgement could result in the selection of certain plates for in a or exclusion of certain plates for inappropriate reasons. When it comes to actually doing the study. Is that like?

Whaley, Paul

Theoretically possible? Or is it just sound completely observed?

Hey, I actually raised my hand for a different reason but and I I don't have direct experience with that but.

I think in the folks that I've worked with who do self based assays, it's not a subjective criteria of whether or not it will be included. It has clear quality requirements of whether a plate will get included or not.

Whaley, Paul

So, but if there weren't clear quality requirements and somebody were making subjective judgments.

Whaley, Paul

Would that be a problem?

Whaley, Paul

What do you think? It's just so unlikely. It's just never gonna happen, so I don't have to worry about it or, you know, is it that it or is the having kind of objective standards for entry a way of ensuring that this seal activity doesn't occur? But if it was occurring, you would be very worried about it.

Whaley, Paul

Just trying to think about which way this kind of concept goes, basically because umm it was very hard for us to figure out how selective inclusion in a study operates in an in vitro context. And we kind of have this some feedback that is like well, I mean you know This is why we have objective criteria for like evaluating the plates or whatever is to prevent this happening. But then if you've got objective criteria to prevent that happening and it's heavily policed then people must be really worried about it.

Whaley, Paul

Which means that it's important. So what, we're just trying to get a sense of do we include this because it's important, even though it's unlikely.

Whaley, Paul

Do we just not include it because it never happens? Or is it just unimportant and we think that it sounds important because there are measures taken to prevent it from happening? And if it does, measures weren't taken, then there would be a serious concern, but at the same time people are saying like we're never concerned about it because these measures always happen. So is it possible to help us navigate that?

Whaley, Paul

It's not mixed message for me, by the way. It's mixed messages from A delphi and just all over the place. So.

Whaley, Paul

You can't shrug for the transcript. You'd have to say it more or no.

Whaley, Paul

That's what I do a lot.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

Oh, I think I think the challenge as I see it is that most assays have clear protocols in place to ensure that whatever material our cells are going into the assay are the quality that's acceptable. So there's not really a subjective selection stage there.

And so that's maybe why there's not a consensus because.

The you know we if you think about it in that process being part of the requirements, then yes, it's important. But if you think about that process being already taken care of, then this would be not important.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. OK. So you'd be in a situation where, like, if you saw her in a study that those processes hadn't been taken care of, you'd be very, very concerned. So you'd be like, potentially extremely high risk of bias. If you've seen they were taken care of, you'd be thinking it was a low risk of bias just in this particular domain or for this particular reason. And that's sort of how you'd be thinking about it.

Experimental designs, but that becomes very important. Like if you have to have certain number of like a certain cell count or something to run the assay. So I could see scenarios where that's important. I just personally didn't, didn't really deal with that but.

And that's I can see where for certain study designs that's important too.

To be vigilant about that.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

And transparent.

Whaley, Paul

Participant, we will get back to your point. You raise your hand for a moment ago as well, just to rush.

Whaley, Paul

Oh, OK.

Oh well, that I was just putting my hand up for that point. So if we're ready to go there, I'll go. But if there's more comments on this, I'll, I'll wait.

Whaley, Paul

So I think I'm happy that we can progress with this. So I think we've got enough information to have a good plan here on our side. So Participant, your hand, thank you for being patient.

Yeah, I wanted to circle back to what Participant said about, you know, the rejection or retention of samples being based on the performance for the negative controls.

So I think this is an important point.

In in vitro, because oftentimes in the work that I've done in the the work I'm familiar with, we don't necessarily select or reject a sample or plate until we see the actual performance, just because there is, there are so many samples happening at any given time. And so making that decision to retain or reject a sample happens after we see some of the performance data and that can be.

I mean it's if you are going to reject samples at that level, it should be databased. You know, based on the you know the performance and some metrics that are acceptable performance versus not acceptable. But I have seen scenarios in the folks I work with where they well it just didn't look right and so that would be very subjective and I said well we can't, we can't, we can't say that in the paper. So why are you rejecting it? And if you can't describe.

A based on the results we're seeing, then we have to keep it in.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So I think there's not much on attrition under selection bias and most of the attrition bias issues. So this is the the issue of.

Whaley, Paul

Of samples being excluded, like during the study or when data is being collected rather than an entry point. So sort of exclusion exit that was very good consensus on for the reasons you've just articulated. It was the selection entry where we were struggling to see where consensus was much less clear. And I think it's just because the issue is difficult to differentiate the two.

Whaley, Paul

And it's difficult to see. Yeah. So I think the discussion has been very illuminating for kind of figuring out what was going on behind that consensus process. So yes, I think we're in a good position to proceed there.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

On that note, I think the point I was trying to make it maybe I wasn't clear, is that the lack of consensus here is I think because most of that retention or rejection for in vitro assays that I've seen has been done on the going outside, there's a lot less on the entry side.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I think that's that's a good explanation. Yeah. So where people are most familiar with making the judgement calls is where more attention is focused and where there's less attention focused, you're going to see less consensus. So good.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. Then the other slightly more trivial thing was this use of the word participant. So I think certainly one of the previous groups, we found that if we replace the word participant with sample or suddenly the problem disappeared.

Whaley, Paul

But we'll go through some specific examples here and we can see how well that works in this particular case.

Whaley, Paul

OK. So item 222, we're going to be revisiting some of the things we just discussed, but this will help us make decisions. So item 222.

Whaley, Paul

Relates to, I think came from probably one of the more recent risk of buy assessment instruments for.

Whaley, Paul

Controlled Rct's and people, right? So.

Whaley, Paul

Also no B from Robins. That's what I think actually thinking about it, because you've got.

Whaley, Paul

It's basically to do to do with.

Whaley, Paul

You've got exposure window starts before the study, right?

Whaley, Paul

So let's see, there's expens.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, exposure window starts before the study. To be honest, I think having had the discussion we've got, I can see that this one probably just doesn't make any sense because this is, there's not really any

clear way in which you could start the exposure. Are there any studies where you've got the exposure selection to in vitro study starting after exposure has happened?

0:45:14.815 --> 0:45:18.855

Whaley, Paul

I mean, maybe you could get experience how you want, but yeah.

Sure. Yeah. If you had a exposure in an animal model and then you move it to.

You know you take the primary cells and do an assay with them.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

I guess that makes sense.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So that could be typing.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

So I was thinking about some of these. When you use the word participant to try to make sense in my mind how it would work in a in vitro system or experiment.

Whaley, Paul

I think this one group could apply with primary cell cultures but.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, my brain goes to Marsh when I think about how this could work. When the in vitro context say.

Whaley, Paul

OK. Uh, in case influenced by outcome status. So this would relate to.

Whaley, Paul

So maybe an analogue for in vitro studies here where you know quite often in human healthcare research.

Whaley, Paul

People who are sicker tend to be more likely to be included in a study and historically tended to be more likely given the treatment than the control right? Because if someone is not well, you want them to be given the drugs rather than the test drugs rather than the control drugs.

Whaley, Paul

And that biases the study, right?

Whaley, Paul

So.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. Or you're just recruiting from a sicker proportion of the population rather than, say, healthier portion or something like that. Are there any in vitro designs where you could conceivably be selecting samples because they are?

Whaley, Paul

More likely or already showing the outcome that you're potentially interested in.

Whaley, Paul

Than otherwise. So yeah, again, you end up with this selection biases. It's a systematic differences between the.

Whaley, Paul

Samples in the.

Whaley, Paul

But in in the control arm versus the different exposure groups? Or does that just sound like it's just not possible because of the way the studies are done?

No, I don't think it's possible on my side.

Whaley, Paul

Like you wouldn't be testing the cells for, you know some observation or so you test them all for some particular characteristic at the beginning of the study, and then after you've done that, you allocate them to the exposure and control arms. So this different exposure groups.

Whaley, Paul

And that your knowledge of them exhibiting a certain characteristic or something, or performing a certain way, then influences that allocation procedure. Nothing like that.

Whaley, Paul

That.

Yeah, I don't think it's possible to if you are because with a lot of in vitro we say at the end you have all the same cells everywhere in your plate. So and you treat or not, that's you don't select and it's very homogeneous.

Self contents, so I'm not sure.

Yeah, I don't think there are any trouble with this type of gas.

Whaley, Paul

What about are there?

Whaley, Paul

Essays where it could be relevant, so we're going to talk with our culture's right. But maybe if there were some visible indicators of cell health or something, like if you're.

Whaley, Paul

I don't know. Like if you're I. I've noticed in vitro researcher. So just bear with me while I say things that are stupid. But imagine like, you know, looking at cell confluence or something under a microscope and some of those cells, you know, look a bit confident is OK. But they look a bit sick. So you're like, OK, well, we'll put those over this side. And then these ones look for healthy, put them over that side and end up with a difference. I mean, that's Participant's laughing at me. So that probably is ridiculous, but.

Yeah, but.

Well, I think I I don't. Oh, go ahead.

No, no, no, no. Kitty fat. Yeah, let's go.

I don't. I don't do cell based assays, but from the folks I work with that do that, that's ridiculous because there's just clear criteria. If there's not adequate quality of cells, they don't get included in any of the treatments.

Yeah, but.

Whaley, Paul

But what if there's like, but you could have presume if you got adequate policy, but then you could have like better than adequate quality, right? So you could be putting the adequates over here and the really, really great looking ones over here, right? Could that conceivably happen?

But in.

In your in your. Yeah, yeah.

Sorry, usually for up song go ahead Participant.

Whaley, Paul

Participant, you go first and then they say that you're helpful.

Yeah, but yeah, just one point you have because I I use a lot of different cell line and cell models and whatever in 2D, in 3D and whatever. But when you use your plate.

All well are the same with the same type of cells in the same level of proliferation or whatever and whatever. And you have your control negative positive and you have your treatment and so.

And you run them everything and you make three times independently. The experiment. So and you don't choose which point or so maybe you could have difference between the triplicate if effectively one days of sale are not so good or whatever, but it will be random and it will be the same for positive and negative control so.

I think it's not the as as obvious will be report everywhere and.

And yeah, I think it's not a trouble on my side.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm. OK, Participant.

Yeah, I know. I was just gonna say that. I mean, I just, I think, I guess it's possible. It feels like a little bit of a stretch. I think I agree that you. I mean when you're just depending on the experimental design you have like, you know, you play a certain number of cells for a particular assay and you kind of look for.

You know how? How do they look? And a lot of it is visual inspection. I can see that. But I don't know if it's.

I don't know. It feels it feels like this might be a little bit of a stretch and also hard to evaluate in this context.

Whaley, Paul

There's like quite a grand point we we understand the potential issue of like selective inclusion, but maybe going into this level of detail just maybe isn't particularly helpful, Participant.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

And there may not be consensus on these, in particular, for the reason we are talking about on the previous slide, which is that these are pieces that you know the inclusion of samples in the results and the analysis can be influenced by characteristics that are required them to be thrown out. You know, there are wells that just fail to meet the standard procedure and you don't know why you don't necessarily know, they may be missed a reagent or something happened.

So that could have led to the lack of consensus here.

Because I personally may have been reading these and thinking how to translate this into samples and thinking about if we saw well that had no change. So in the assets I've done them both or it's a colour change. So if they had no change during the exposure then we know something went wrong in that well and we would exclude it from the analysis. So again, it's maybe on the outcome side versus the entry side.

And that may have led to some.

Varying ranges of answers on these.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I find this very difficult to interpret for the human EPI and this time going to the big, easy, straightforward study designs.

Whaley, Paul

So I can see why it's why it's challenging. OK. So I think we've got good reason here for thinking this probably can be excluded. I suspect we've got this idea of timing participant follow up. Again this might have been just an issue of like the just a complete mismatch within vitro study designs which drove the lack of consensus like mismatched the bio people didn't understand what on Earth it was talking about. So it ended up no consensus out of exclude.

Whaley, Paul

So timing participant follow up.

Whaley, Paul

Relates to when.

Whaley, Paul

Outcome status is measured in.

Whaley, Paul

A study participant, right? So.

Whaley, Paul

The longer you leave it, say, with some diseases, the more likely the disease is to be severe.

Whaley, Paul

And that could introduce a bias into the study if you sort of drawing conclusions about the effects of the treatment, something on that basis.

Whaley, Paul

Is there any way in which there's something analogous with like?

Whaley, Paul

You know.

Whaley, Paul

And then in vitro study, you don't, do you have any anything in outlook just to follow up, we just have like you know you just run the assay imagine the outcome at a certain point in time and it's job done right, Participant?

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Yeah, for sure. I'd uh, it will depends of the timing. But normally in your protocol you check if you have a 24 hours or three day repeat treatment or just six hour treatment. So it's fixed at the beginning of the treatment. So and everything is the same for every experiment so.

I'm not sure it's.

This applied to individual ation.

Whaley, Paul

I suspect that because it's a controlled environment, this idea of tying participant follow up doesn't apply grew, so we should probably just check that.

Whaley, Paul

But I suspect that this one can be eliminated.

Whaley, Paul

Random allocation we've discussed in detail if it said samples to exposure groups, would that make a bit more sense to you?

Whaley, Paul

Yep. And given that makes sense, would it be in our previous discussion, would it be the kind of thing that you think we should be including in?

Whaley, Paul

The tool potentially, even if it's a rare occurrence issue.

Whaley, Paul

I'm thinking.

I I think so. And even if you're in the scenario where you're doing serial dilutions, you still have your positive and negative controls. That ideally would be randomised.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

There it goes, OK.

Whaley, Paul

So what are things that have to like a loaf? Obviously, another low consensus thing is this idea of inappropriate confluence threshold.

Whaley, Paul

So this would be somebody setting a conference threshold for eligibility of or inclusion of all over well or played into a study.

Whaley, Paul

I guess I was a bit surprised that this didn't have consensus because it would seem that setting of confidence threshold incorrectly would be kind of a big deal in a study. But Participant, maybe you can explain.

Whaley, Paul

M.

No, I think it's a. It is a big deal, but it is for a specific subset of in vitro studies types. So I'm assuming this would just be for cell based assays and there's a lot of other types of in vitro assays.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

That was my concern about that, that one.

Whaley, Paul

OK. Yep, Participant.

We also it depends on the cell type. It depends also all the endpoint you you check and as mentioned before and as mentioned by Participant, you have always your positive and negative control. So at the end if there are any trouble with the cell or with the experiment, not that they with your positive and negative control then OK, you just delete all the the plate or all the SA and you rerun a new experiment.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

OK.

Whaley, Paul

So I think that it sounds like it goes in. There has been some discussion of potentially making the invites into a modular so.

Whaley, Paul

That you'd have different questions or different prompts for different study designs. So obviously the major kind of modular approach would be kind of an invites in for primary cell cultures because some of the issues are so different that you'd kind of almost want a different tool.

Whaley, Paul

But then there's also like.

Whaley, Paul

You know, dividing it up according to self exists. Study design was a bit like Ohare does for its Rob tool where you have different questions for different types of observational study.

Whaley, Paul

Or animals? Sorry, different, different question that was very.

Whaley, Paul

Design designs. So we're thinking about doing that. So that may be another way of dealing with issues like confluence threshold and may be specific to particular.

Whaley, Paul

Assays and we can hide that off and say, OK, if you're doing this study design then answer this set of questions at this point or something like that.

Whaley, Paul

Uh, then inappropriate retention of compromised samples. Presumably that's important. Again, like we didn't see consensus on that for some reason, but again, it felt like it was kind of be an obvious big deal if you had compromise samples and you'd kept them in your study. But Participant?

I think with with both of these last two, some of the concern is defining inappropriate. And as Participant was describing, that could vary a lot depending on the.

The cells or the sample types.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

And so maybe.

Maybe some of us were just getting stuck on, you know, how would you define inappropriate in rather than letting that be a professional judgement to say, what is it inappropriate at the point of the evaluation?

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, we'll get to that when we design the tool.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, I think so. Sometimes this language of inappropriate is kinda stayed in like after the normalisation process and maybe when normalising the items we could have removed all any kind of judgement related language or like for that the next time we only spent three months normalising. So kind of.

Whaley, Paul

Thought that to be really hard to do.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. OK. So I think we can understand what's happened there as well. So that's relating to the inappropriateness term, but obviously retention of compromise samples would be a problem, right? If I understand correctly, you know getting some lots there, so that will do, OK, right. So two items left.

Whaley, Paul

It may well be done for the end of the hour and a half so.

Whaley, Paul

This is the timing of study termination bias domain, so that is a bias due to the decision to end the study earlier or later than planned. So just two items under this, no, we didn't get good consensus.

Whaley, Paul

Again, it's this term about the term inappropriate driving some of that lack of consensus and then the relevance of early study termination in vitro studies. So just two items. So we probably discuss these in some detail. So we've got.

Whaley, Paul

For a decision to continue collecting data after study was planned to be terminated.

Whaley, Paul

If we take out the word inappropriate decision and we just say something like continuing to collect data after study was planned to be terminated or finished, right, so that might be, you know you in your study plan you're saying, well, we'll we'll collect like some data at 120 seconds and then you collect data and 20 seconds and you go actually we're going to collect data 140 seconds and then collect the data then instead.

Whaley, Paul

The that could introduce bias into a study.

Whaley, Paul

Is that something that could conceivably happen in in vitro contacts?

Whaley, Paul

Or even if you're planning to do it at 120 and then just because of the physical mechanics of measuring stuff, you end up taking 130 seconds to do it or something, getting a little bit of nodding. But Participant.

So I definitely got stuck on these and the scenario that I got stuck on is that so for most of the in vitro assays that I've run and that I am aware of, there's a clear protocol that says you basically you're unexposed for this long and then your measurements happen at this period and sometimes there are multiple measurements that are taken through that time period and.

It could be that you don't know, so you take take take measurements for 5 minutes every minute or every 30 seconds, and you don't necessarily know when you're collecting the data, which is the optimum time point for the measurement. And then the data will tell you where the optimum time point is. And so this.

Like I just got wrapped around on this idea of. There's not usually a time, so most of them have protocols that have clear study durations or have a clear like you run the study until this happens, but then the actual data reporting and analysis point may be at any point within there and I just got stuck on that. I'm not sure if that made sense to everyone or not, but it's.

In my experience, there's not any any opportunity to stop or continue collecting data because there's clear protocols on the timing. However, there are scenarios where you may collect data for longer and use a earlier time point for for actual results.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm. OK, we can continue discussing this, Participant.

Yeah, normally you have a strict protocol, so you have a defined timing to for the treatment and for the measurement and whatever. And for a long period.

24 hours normally if you.

Search at 23 or 25 hours. I think it will not change most of thing for very short period. For other endpoint. Maybe it could have a clear impact but as mentioned before when you have in the same experiment positive and negative results.

Control no money and you have a triplicate to a biological triplicate at the end. You have just a variation at the end, so I think it's not a trouble.

Whaley, Paul
Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul
OK. Have you seen them?

I just I have a hard time with this because I mean, even if you deviate from let's say, a standard particle, which can happen because I mean laboratory conditions are different, sometimes you would take a standard protocol and adapt it to your experimental design, etcetera. And you make changes. But you do report those in your like in your paper, in your methods. If you deviate or if you extend the collection time or anything, that's something that will be reported, right. So it's not.

Unless you purposely try to hide that, but I just don't see why that would be the case. I don't know.

Right.

Whaley, Paul
Well, you wouldn't necessarily hide it, right? You might just extend the data collection time to be completely open, but it could still be a problem I mean.

And you would be, I mean, but sometimes you do need to, I mean, again, based on differences in laboratory conditions, et cetera, or you may take a standardised portable for something and you might adapt it for your specific assay. I mean, we often did that in the lab where you you.

Were you were constantly adapting protocols.

I mean.

Whaley, Paul
So I guess the thing here is whether or not the impacts on the potential for.

Whaley, Paul
You know, introducing error systematic error into a study, right? So the concern analogous concern in like say it's again in healthcare research, right is that?

Whaley, Paul
You there's several ways of appropriate of doing this, so one way of doing it'd be like OK, we're going to give this pill to these, this group of people for six months, right? We're going to hopefully reduce their risk of heart attacks, but obviously we're not going to see very many heart attacks in this group of people over a six month period because it's quite rare and these people relatively healthy.

Whaley, Paul
So we're going to look for bioParticipanters of heart health, right. And then so they go six months and they're like, OK, so the bioParticipanters for heart health haven't really changed. So what we're going to do is we're going to carry on this study for another two months and then measure them again, right. And then after another two months, lo and behold, there's been a slight improvement in bioParticipanters of heart health. So they stopped the study and they published results after eight months rather than the six months planned. Right. So then there's a question, OK, is the improvement heart health?

Whaley, Paul
Just random chance because.

Whaley, Paul

They are cause of a decision to stop the study bit later. Or is it actually a result of the treatment they were given? And it's very hard to tell, right?

Whaley, Paul

They were originally going to do it for six months and presumably for good reason, and then they extended bit and they stop it. Not because.

Whaley, Paul

Have a plan, but just because of the results they happen to be seeing, right?

Whaley, Paul

So that would.

Whaley, Paul

Of obvious and serious concern, if you're looking at that study in people, are there any circumstances? And I think in Participant it was sound to me a little bit like you're talking about a situation that may be analogous to this where you run the essay longer and then you see a result and then you stop, right.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah.

Well, no. I think my and maybe something I was thinking about this a little bit differently because even I mean before you adopt A protocol, you sort of do.

This that's pre designed. You're designing your you're adopting something and designing your experiment. That's another thing that once you collect data, you decide. Oh, you know what? Maybe I'm going to run it longer, see what happens. That's a little bit different, I think.

From what I how I was thinking about this.

So yeah, I mean, I can see how this could be problematic if it's something that's not in your initial design and you just happen to extend it.

Yeah, it seems like you'd be up controls in that situation. It would be fine if you have positive and negative controls and they're all run for the same duration.

Whaley, Paul

So.

That would take care of the of the problem, unless you're trying to compare, you know, two studies with different different durations, different designs.

Whaley, Paul

How does the? So you might have to explain to me how the response.

Whaley, Paul

Helps helps in this situation because if we're thinking about this study in with bioParticipanters and people, all the groups are run for longer periods, right. So it's probably going to be a negative control because we're doing it studying people, right. But you've got the negative control. So it's either placebo or like alternative treatment and then they've got the drug and then you run the whole thing for longer.

Whaley, Paul

And you know that in the control, you're not gonna see anything. 'cause. That's the. That's the compaction that you are comparing the bioParticipanters in the exposed in the treatment group to the control group. And over time after eight months you see a small difference. Whereas after six months you don't see a significant statistically significant difference. So the control isn't helping that you still have the bias in spite of the control. So would would so how do the controls, I guess it may be to do with the positive control then, but how would the controls help with this situation in vitro?

Right. Yeah, that sounds like what you're talking about is the study sensitivity issue, so decrease sensitivity.

Whaley, Paul

It.

Whaley, Paul

It might be a detection bias, which is pretty close to select sensitivity, so.

Whaley, Paul

I tend to talk about detection bias instead of sensitivity because I feel like I understand detection bias better, but.

Whaley, Paul

You'd over detecting basically in your uh, in that study 'cause you'd run it for longer.

Whaley, Paul

Participant.

Yeah, I've mentioned for the last point, normally you have a street protocol and you don't change the feeling of the timing of the treatment or when you have to to check for the results you you know that it's 24 hours or it's 12 hours or you you do the the job and you use the street protocol you have in your hand and the protocol you you have in your paper at the end and.

Also, as an ancient before, you have always positive negative control and so on and so on. So normally I I don't think it's a. It's very useful to be include there.

Whaley, Paul

Mm.

We, because I think we all agree that most of the time we do have a standard protocol that's being developed and in in the lab and whatever and and you've presumably optimised.

Could it this be phrased in a way where you deviate from that standard protocol with no providing no justification, or you know something like that?

Whaley, Paul

I mean, I think that's what.

'Cause I can see how this might be an issue. Maybe doesn't happen as often, but I do see that there's opportunity for that too.

Occur if someone's not really being.

Fully transparent.

With that initial protocol and how they used it.

Whaley, Paul

Yeah. So I think I always have these slides around. So I think that's the, that's the whole idea of early or late study termination bias, right is that there was a plan that someone was supposed to stick to, right, and then they didn't stick to that plan. They did something a bit different and then presented the results of doing things differently. And that affects our confidence that the results of that study are true. Right. So in the case of the heart, heart. Yeah.

Well, without any justification exactly. There might be a very.

A fine explanation for that, but if there's no explanation or anything, I think I would still wanna.

I would still want to leave room for.

An explanation without any justification for.

Whaley, Paul

Sure. I mean, at this point, we're not worrying too much about when it's justified and when it isn't and when we're concerned and when we're not specifically, it'll be more like is it theoretically possible.

Whaley, Paul

And you know, if it's possible, how would it be of concern? So, you know, in human trials, it's very much possible and often of a great deal of concern. It's like if I had a top five list of ways of.

Whaley, Paul

Finding out what I wanted from a study manipulating the termination point of the study would be right up there for me. 'cause it's very easy to make effects disappear by stopping a study earlier than planned and make them look more important by carrying on the longer than planned, right?

Whaley, Paul

So I don't like this, but I don't know how this applies in an in vitro context. So Participant.

I just wanted to follow up on some of the comments that Participant said. So if you take a standard protocol and you adapt it for your lab and come up with a new protocol that works in your lab conditions, then that's what you're following. And so any deviation from that new one is what we would be concerned with. Not that you weren't following us a standard or a guideline protocol, right?

Whaley, Paul

Yeah, that seems reasonable. Yeah. I mean, yeah.

OK. Yeah. So that leaves room for that, you know, modification of standard protocols. And then if you deviate from that planned protocol, again, you could be introducing bias, but there may be a very justified reason and it gets back at that judgement on whether it's appropriate or not.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Whaley, Paul

Good. OK. So it does sound like this could mess up and it's just the the important thing here is to emphasise that it's it's not.

Whaley, Paul

Changing some standardised protocol that masses it what matters is funny business in following your own protocol.

Whaley, Paul

Because that can, yeah, lead to, you know, an effect being smaller than it should be or larger than it should be compared to how it ought to be if you did things properly, right, which is what this was always about. OK, good, Participant.

Just one follow up. One of the things that I think I'm also stuck on some of these questions on is that there's a difference between what you're doing when you're in assay development, whether it be in vitro assay or kind of exploratory research where you may be needing to extend your study duration or plan it, stop it earlier because that is very relevant because you don't know what's going to happen. We do that a lot in our amphibian thyroid disruption research because we don't know how the.

Whaley, Paul

Mm hmm.

Compounds are going to influence their developmental rate, so we can't have a planned stopping date in some cases, so that experimental research.

That's that's a struggle with some of these on the kind of experimental research. But once you get into kind of standard.

Application of assays. Then these types of questions I think are are very relevant.

Whaley, Paul

Good. Yes, I think this is something else that we can be much clearer about, right. So most of risk of by assessment happens in the context of doing a systematic review where people are, at least, you know, you've got studies that are included because they are.

Whaley, Paul

Presenting themselves as having investigated exposure outcome relationship in some way, right. So the kind of the exploratory research that was done in kind of assay development and things probably isn't even in the systematic review. And if it is in the systematic review, it's because it can be interpreted as being informative or related to the research question. And then the risk of bias assessment is done because you are trying to understand whether or not the.

Whaley, Paul

The fact size observed in the literature is like the extent to which the fact size is observed might be true or not, right? So again, this is not about whether or this exploratory studies were done appropriately or inappropriately. It's about how the results of those studies can be interpreted for the purpose of the systematic review, which is a different research enterprise and different question. So I think agree we need to make that super clear because again, it's not that we're criticising studies. We're like what we're always doing is repurposing someone else's study for our own research goals now.

Whaley, Paul

Because we don't have the time or resource or whatever to do a whole load of primary research, we think that the answer may already be in the existing studies have already been done, right? So yeah.

Whaley, Paul

It's captured but.

Yeah, in my mind. Yeah, for sure. When you develop a new SA, you don't know what's a precise timing. You need to have the highest level of condition of pure Participant or whatever, and it will

depend of cell type and it will maybe depend of the Selma left you and 2D and 3D. You could have some different timing on that. So maybe you have to to move on. But normally when you have an established.

Protocol I.

It's fine, and normally, whatever when you publish your in vitro results, you will clearly mention that you use a 12 hour 24 hour of. If you modify anything in your protocol. So you will find it. I'm not sure that when you make.

A systemical review. You could have the detail. I'm not sure that's training of the protocol to be sure that the timing is the same in all the 3D you will take into account, but clearly it's very important at the end.

Whaley, Paul

OK, very good. Thank you. So I think we've got enough information to proceed here as well and that takes us to the end of the discussion. So we managed to get through all.